

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth System**

Data Management Plan v.3.0

Deliverable D7.3

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<https://ocean-ice.eu/>

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List of Acronyms

AABW	Antarctic bottom water
AANCHOR	All Atlantic Cooperation for Ocean Research and Innovation
AAPP	Australian Antarctic Program Partnership
ACC	Antarctic Circumpolar Current
AES	Advanced Encryption Standard
AIS	Antarctic Ice Sheet
AMOC	Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation
ApRES	Autonomous Phase-sensitive Radio Echo Sounder
AUV	Autonomous underwater vehicle
AWI	Alfred-Wegener-Institut Helmholtz-Zentrum Fur Polar- Und Meeresforschung
AWS	Automatic weather stations
BSH	Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring System
CNRS	Centre National De La Recherche Scientifique
CNRS-IGE	Centre national de la recherche scientifique - Institut des Géosciences de l'Environnement
DACs	Data archive centres
DATAMEQ	Data Management, Exchange and Quality Working Group
DFFE	Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital object identifier
DU	Dissemination Unit
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EDMERP	European Directory of Marine Environmental Research Projects
EDMO	European Directory of Marine Organisations
EF	Environmental Monitoring Facilities
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EO	Earth Observation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EPCO	European Polar Coordination Office
ESA	European Space Agency
ESMs	Earth System Model
FAIR	Findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable
FESOM	Finite-Element/volumE Sea ice-Ocean Model
FOSS	Free and open-source software
GCM	Generic Conceptual Model
GNOS	GeoNetwork open-source
GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System
INS	In situ
INSPIRE	Infrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe
IODE	International Oceanographic Data and Information Exchange
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ITGC	International Thwaites Glacier Collaboration

JARE	Japanese Antarctic Research Expedition
JRC	Joint Research Centre
NEMO	Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
NMO	Numerical models
NORCE	Norwegian Research Centre
NorESM	Norwegian Earth System Model
NPI	Norwegian Polar Institute
O&M	Observations and Measurements
OBP	Ocean best practices
OCG	Observation Coordination Group
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OF	Oceanographic Geographical Features
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor IDentifier
PISM-MOM	Parallel Ice Sheet Model-Modular Ocean Model
RCM	Real climate model
SAMBA	South Atlantic MOC Basin-wide Array
SAON	Sustaining Arctic Observing Network
SEANOE	Sea Open Scientific Data Publication
SLR	Sea level rise
SMB	Surface mass balance
SMOS	Soil Moisture and Ocean Salinity
SR	Sea Regions
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
SSP	Shared socio-economic pathway
TICs	Turbulence instrument clusters
TipMip	Tipping Point Model Intercomparison Project
UGOT	University of Gothenburg
UKESM	The UK Earth System Modelling project
UKRI-BAS	United Kingdom Research and Innovation - British Antarctic Survey
ULB	Université Libre de Bruxelles
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
UNIVBRIS	University of Bristol
UNN	University of Northumbria at Newcastle
UoS	University of Southampton
UREAD	University of Reading
VM	Virtual machine
WAF	Web Accessible Folder
WOA	World Ocean Assessment
WP	Work package

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1. Publishable summary

OCEAN ICE provides products to both internal and external users. The data workflow is based on a chain of individual operational components, each contributing either to data production or user interaction functions. The infrastructure provides open and free data access, adopting international standards and following European regulations, such as INSPIRE. It is accessible under the OCEAN ICE web domain (www.ocean-ice.eu) and offers up-to-date means of data dissemination and interaction tools.

Nevertheless, the developed system cannot be considered finally closed, and for the entire duration of the project, the following evolution principles have to be considered and applied:

- **The service shall be state-of-the-art in its scope, and it shall be user-driven.**

All service capabilities are defined, allocated, and implemented with sound and state-of-the-art technical and scientific justifications, addressing the needs of both OCEAN ICE internal and external users. If new needs arise, it is essential to try to match them (whenever possible).

Providing international-level, state-of-the-art tools entails constantly monitoring and applying the most suitable methodologies at any given time to meet the requirements for service quality in data processing, validation, and other related areas.

- **Common standards are adopted and applied throughout the different elements of the system.**

Standards are identified, adopted and applied. If, during the lifetime of the project, rising ocean best practices (OBP) become standards, the project has to try to include, as much as possible, these new OBP.

The system evolves constantly in response to service requirements, scientific and technical requirements, marine environment products requirements, and stakeholders' requirements.

In this context, the Ocean Best Practices System (OBPS) provides a global, FAIR-aligned framework to share and adopt methodologies in ocean observing and modelling. The project will contribute by submitting its practices and guidelines, enhancing their visibility, interoperability, and reproducibility.

At the European level, initiatives such as EuroSea and JERICO-S3 have strengthened OBPS by supporting endorsement processes and improving access and discoverability. The new EuroGOOS data policy (European Global Ocean Observing System, 2023), hosted in OBPS, further illustrates the European commitment to making ocean data openly available under FAIR principles. Moreover, the European Commission, through its executive agency European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA), is developing the European Contribution to the OBPS (ECOBPSS, <https://ecobpss-pre.ctnaval.com/home>), an integrated information system to collect and disseminate standards and best practices in ocean observation. By engaging with OBPS and ECOBPSS, the project aligns with European and international frameworks, ensuring harmonisation, transparency, and long-term sustainability.

- **The quality of the workflow methodology must follow and apply well-established engineering methodologies derived from industry (e.g., ISO 9001:2015, ISO 15288, etc.) to drive the definition of an adapted approach.**

Data management also adopts good practices and methodologies to ensure system monitoring, fixing and reporting.

Within this framework, OCEAN ICE positions itself amongst the up-to-date data infrastructure projects, adopts the latest interoperability best practices and enables data-products FAIRness to maximise the OCEAN ICE data value chain from production to its end use for added value ocean products.

The DMP is a living document, and this deliverable presents the updated version of the OCEAN ICE DMP. To facilitate the reader's understanding of the latest changes with respect to Version 2, the updates are highlighted in green.

The text highlighted in yellow instead points at the changes that were introduced in Version 2 with respect to Version 1.

2. Scope of the document

This document presents the updated version of the OCEAN ICE Data Management Plan (DMP). It extends the preliminary version of the OCEAN ICE DMP (D7.2) that is based on the Horizon Europe Data Management Plan (DMP) template.

OCEAN ICE moves beyond open access in implementing open science practices while following Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability (FAIR) principles. It applies to research data collected during the project as well as to publications. OCEAN ICE is running a Zenodo community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/oceanice>) that hosts all new collected and produced datasets and products. Newly collected in situ data are also federated to key marine data integrators (EMODnet) and OCEANICE stakeholders' marine data integrator systems (e.g. SOOS).

To this end, OCEAN ICE data management (WP7) uses tools that organise data in the OCEAN ICE backend system, which provides immediate and free access to collected data. The Backend is based on open data management software tools (e.g. ERDDAP, GeoServer, GeoNetwork), which are complemented by open science extensions (e.g., Python codes and colab notebooks) ⁽¹⁾ which are documented under the project web pages ⁽²⁾. Data come with a metadata model that utilises controlled vocabularies (e.g., BODC-NVS) and EU or international standards (e.g., ISO).

The project developed data management software tools that are made freely available under Creative Commons/open data commons licencing.

The document recalls the scope of the OCEAN ICE project. It describes the OCEAN ICE framework for research data management in accordance with the requirements of Article 17 of the Grant Agreement. These include description of data (data summary), approach to FAIRness, research outputs, allocation of resources, security and ethics.

Document Disclaimers:

This document is based on the Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Template [V1.1 April 2022] and adapted to provide the OCEAN ICE partners and OCEAN ICE stakeholders a living guide for the project Data Management Plan. The Community is not responsible for any use that might be made of the content of this publication.

3. Data summary

The timely, free, and unrestricted exchange of oceanographic observational data is essential for understanding the oceans' complex role in the weather and climate, as well as for empowering decision-makers with evidence-based information for the sustainable management of the ocean and its environment. An open and free data policy is widely encouraged by the European Commission and Member States for a wide range of environmental data services targeted at a wide range of user communities. Interoperability of data systems has become a priority with the development of FAIR principles (2014) (<https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>), a set of guiding principles (2016) to make data **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable**.

¹ <https://github.com/s4oceanice/literacy.s4oceanice>

² <https://s4oceanice.eu/demo/intro.html>

Furthermore, in 2021, the OECD, with the Recommendation on Enhancing Access to and Sharing of Data, set principles and policy guidance to help governments maximise the cross-sectoral benefits of all types of data – personal, non-personal, open, proprietary, public, and private – while protecting the rights of individuals and organisations.

The availability and accessibility of these data are not always easy. Often, the sources lack compliance with international standards, and many challenges (still) exist associated with good management of ocean data, such as using different formats, a wide diversity of datasets, and disparate data management structures, among others (Tanhua et al., 2019). Anyhow, the basic milestones are set and can be easily adopted and adapted to the purpose. This comprises open science practices covering the entire workflow of the ocean data production and dissemination, including data processing, validation and dissemination infrastructure(s).

3.1 Purpose of data generation/reuse

The objective of OCEAN ICE is to assess the impacts of key Antarctic Ice Sheet and Southern Ocean processes, studying their influence on sea level rise, deep water formation, ocean circulation and climate. OCEAN ICE uses a combination of old and new observations and numerical models.

OCEAN ICE is planning a set of quasi-simultaneous circumpolar observations over periods of several years [2022-2024]. Old and new data are both in situ and remote sensing observations. New observations are addressed in circumpolar and Atlantic areas to reduce current gaps. These observations are used to feed models and produce new estimates of (the giant) ice sheet melt and impacts on ocean circulation (including the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation – AMOC), global sea level rise and other critical climate parameters over the coming decades and centuries. OCEAN ICE uses already available coupled ice sheet-climate models and develops/advances these models.

The figure shows the OCEAN ICE structure and the addressed goals:

Fig. 1: OCEAN ICE structure and addressed goals (April 2024).

Where WP1-WP6, WP10 and WP11 are the data and product generators. Each WP is organised into tasks, and each task is either producing, assessing or developing a data/product:

Fig. 2: Pert Chart (April 2024).

The figure indicates the fundamental process studies in WP1, WP2, WP3, WP10, and WP11. These studies support the construction and analysis of the model (WP4-6) and the structured nature of the experimental design.

3.2 Novel data and re-use of data

As anticipated in the previous section, OCEAN ICE is organised in WPs and tasks, each (WP1-WP6) task consumes or produces data products, being in one of these three main categories:

- 1) In situ (INS) observational data (including reanalysis and virtual in situ observational sites).
- 2) satellite-derived Earth Observational (EO) products.
- 3) Numerical models (NMO).

Tab. 1. Summary of categories of data products for each OCEAN ICE work package.

	INS	EO	NMO
WP1	X	X	X
WP2	X		X
WP3	X	X	X
WP4			X
WP5	X		X
WP6			X
WP10	X		X
WP11	X	X	X

In **WP1, “Subpolar circulation, heat delivery and water mass export”**, and in **WP10, “Subpolar circulation, heat delivery and water mass export”**, OCEAN ICE targets address the key processes, connectivity and circulation of the Antarctic shelf seas. More specifically, OCEAN ICE proposes an ambitious circumpolar programme of instrument deployments, including mooring and novel profiling float arrays over the continental shelf.

WP1 will assess:

- Dynamic Processes:
 - a) Aggregate existing and complement circumpolar mooring records;
 - b) Gathering sea ice formation time series complemented with historical shipboard surveys and numerical model experiments (1979-present hindcast);
 - c) Analyse tides and eddy kinetic energy on Antarctic shelf seas;
 - d) Assess energy propagation from one shelf sea to another with continental shelf waves based on new virtual and regular mooring observations;
 - e) Assess shelf waves, dynamics and local thermodynamics with satellite-based SSH records and sea ice formation time series.
- Advective processes linking and impacting adjacent shelf seas:
 - a) Novel float deployments;
 - b) Prepare and evaluate a 1979-present FESOM model hindcast with data from novel float deployments in sparsely observed regions;

- c) Assess circumpolar connectivity through the coastal current and along-slope circulation via zonal fluxes of energy and freshwater across flux gates between adjacent shelf seas.
- The Southern Ocean as a heat source for glacial melt:
 - a) On the continental slope front, processes regulate the transfer of ocean heat to the ice shelf.
 - b) Quantification of shelf edge fluxes leading to the observed ocean heat content variability in the Amundsen/Bellingshausen sector.
- Shelf Seas as a dense water source for the global thermohaline circulation:
 - a) FESOM hindcast will be used to investigate dense water formation, variability and pathways in the Ross and Weddell Seas.
 - b) Formation on seasonal to interannual time scales, complemented with long-term ocean records and tracer-based water mass age and meltwater fractions;
 - c) Deployment of new oceanographic moorings to identify trends and variabilities in the bottom water outflows.

WP10 will assess:

- The hydrological structure of the marine environment waters of the Northwest Weddell Sea:
 - a) Deploy profiling floats and mooring equipment to monitor water mass transportation pathways;
 - b) Calibrate purchased equipment for observation locations.

OCEAN ICE members and partners make available and consume data from existing mooring arrays in the Amundsen Sea (UKRI-BAS), eastern (KOPRI) and western Ross Sea (NIWA).

The new sensors and platforms from OCEAN ICE are:

- Floats and ice-capable floats,
- AUV missions,
- Ship-based transects,
- cavity turbulence (UKRI-BAS) and oxygen isotopes measurements,
- continuous measurement of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ water isotope ratios,
- turbulence instrument clusters,
- cavity hydrography and helium isotopes observations,
- AABW salinity and transport variability monitoring, by adding sensors in the SAMBA array.

These sensors and platforms are vastly expanding the monitoring capacity in the Southern Oceans and enabling the development of several derived data collections and products by aggregating and complementing with (the reuse of) current, hydrographic and bottom pressure sensors from historical regular mooring observations (led by AWI, UKRI-BAS, CNRS, NPI and NORCE) and new virtual data upstream, in front of and under the Filchner ice shelf, thereby covering the other key sector of abyssal water formation and variability³.

Recent studies demonstrate the viability of shelf sea float deployments where seabed parking between casts is used to minimise drift and allow float operation as full-depth virtual moorings, even in ice-covered regions⁴. More specifically, WP1 will deploy three pairs of ice-capable floats in areas

³ Naughten et al. (2021) - <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-22259-0>

⁴ Wallace et al. (2020) - 10.1029/2020GL087019

that are currently poorly observed and represent important links between regions of significant ice-ocean interaction.

One pair will be deployed between the Amundsen and the Ross Sea (KOPRI supported), to connect upstream and downstream moored arrays and the other two pairs along the East Antarctic margin near the Denman Glacier (AAPP/GEOMAR), and the Totten Ice Shelf (JARE).

The resulting time series ensemble, coherently covering at least the 2020-2024 time period (and 2009-present in the Amundsen Sea).

WP1 uses satellite-based SSH to assess Shelf waves, dynamics and local thermodynamics propagation and sea ice formation time series. WP1 will use numerical model experiments (1979-present hindcast), complemented with data from novel float deployments in sparsely observed regions, and assess circumpolar connectivity through the coastal current and along-slope circulation via zonal fluxes of energy and freshwater across flux gates between adjacent shelf seas.

Agreements with national float deployment programs (e.g. German ARGO programme), past success by project members in acquiring floats through national float procurement programmes (e.g. CNRS) and partner co-deployments and data sharing arrangements (e.g. partners AAPP) are anticipated to significantly enhance the OCEAN ICE owned array to ~20 floats, including CNRS obtained deep (>4000m) ARGO floats. Additional float pairs will be deployed near moorings for intercomparison/calibration, in additional locations along East Antarctica (the most significant data gap), and west of the Fimbul ice shelf to track signals as they propagate towards the Filchner-Ronne. Expected deep floats will be deployed in the outflow regions from the Ross (Cape Adare) and the Weddell Seas to observe AABW pathways.

FESOM hindcast will be used to investigate dense water formation on seasonal to interannual time scales, complemented with long-term ocean records and tracer-based water mass age and meltwater fractions. Identify trends and variabilities in the bottom water outflows using new oceanographic moorings and establish or refute connections with multidecadal freshening trends.

WP10 will deploy profiling floats and mooring equipment to monitor water mass transportation pathways from the NASC research vessel Noosfera during the Antarctic seasons 2024-2025 and 2025-2026.

In addition, WP10 will share best practices in operating instrumentation, post-processing of data and research skills. Training and knowledge exchange will be organised at AWI, BAS, and on Noosfera, focusing on the operation of oceanographic instrumentation, post-processing and analysis of data, and science related to the thermohaline structure of regional water masses, the transformation of shelf water, and the formation of the frontal zone in the Bransfield Strait.

In WP2, “Cryosphere-ocean interaction, processes and feedbacks”, OCEAN ICE focuses on the key role that ice sheet-ocean interaction plays in melting ice shelves and the export and freshwater distribution of icebergs. WP2 targets to:

- Improved representation of icebergs in ESMs:
 - a) Develop and enhance the iceberg module in NEMO;
 - b) Assessed in regional and global simulations to investigate the model recreation of observed Bear Ridge icebergs and attached sea ice, and increased iceberg discharge at regional to global scales.
- Observing the ocean beneath the sea ice fastened to grounded icebergs:
 - a) Several 24h missions of the UGOT-AUV to explore the Bear Ridge area.

- Observing the ocean near and within ice-shelf cavities:
 - a) Ship-based transects and the AUV near and under the front of Thwaites or Dotson ice shelf, measuring the exchange of properties and ice draft and bathymetry;
 - b) Incorporates UGOT historical data from the ITGC project 2019-2022.
- Observing the ice-shelf/ocean interface of a cold cavity:
 - a) Deploy instrumentation to measure cavity turbulence (UKRI-BAS) and oxygen isotopes (CNRS-IGE) on Fimbul ice shelf via NPI boreholes and logistics.
- Using water isotopes to tune better and evaluate ocean models:
 - a) Develop NEMO capacity to represent ice-shelf meltwater isotopes;
 - b) Tested in a regional model configuration constrained by global surface isotopic concentrations.

WP2 develops and improves the iceberg module in NEMO, improves NEMO capacity to represent ice-shelf meltwater isotopes, and delivers novel observations of the processes controlling ice sheet-ocean interactions under and immediately around warm (Amundsen Sea region) and cold (Fimbul) ice shelves.

Cool ice shelf observations will be made through boreholes on the Fimbul Ice Shelf (2023/24 season), supported by project members NPI⁵. Two OCEAN ICE instruments will be deployed within the ice shelf cavity. Firstly, a novel instrument developed at CNRS, providing continuous measurement of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ water isotope ratios, will be deployed in the Antarctic for the first time. This will give a new method of determining mixing, melting and refreezing across the ocean boundary layer beneath the ice shelf, expanding recent applications of this novel tracer within the region⁶. Secondly, three UKRI-BAS turbulence instrument clusters (TICs) will be deployed across a basal channel: one at the channel centre, one on the channel flank, and one outside the channel extent. This yearlong deployment will measure basal melt rates and resolve the turbulent scalar and momentum fluxes in the ice shelf-ocean boundary layer responsible for driving basal melting. OCEAN ICE observations will be complemented by contemporaneous NPI observations of the cavity hydrography and helium isotopes. Together, these observations will elucidate the mixing and turbulent dynamics of the ice shelf-ocean boundary layer and their impacts on basal melting, which is key to the development of next-generation melt rate parameterisations and model tracer representation.

A Hugin autonomous underwater vehicle (AUV) operated by UGOT (deployed by KOPRI, 2022/23 season) will be used to acquire new hydrographic and bathymetric data from the ice shelf cavities of Thwaites, Dotson, and/or Pine Island Glaciers, as well as the iceberg 'graveyard' on Bear Ridge. This builds on previous successful missions to the area⁷ and focuses on the region near the calving front, where dynamical constraints are active and pose limitations for the warm water inflow⁸ in addition to the active water mass mixing and modification which take place here.¹⁶

Few hydrographic transects have been performed near the ice shelf fronts and even fewer in the high-risk areas where icebergs are stranded in large numbers, such as Bear Ridge. There are still large areas where the bathymetry is poorly known, including the critical ice shelf cavities⁹. OCEAN ICE is going to run to Ship-based transects and the AUV near and under the front of Thwaites or Dotson ice shelf.

⁵ Hattermann et al. (2020) - <https://doi.org/10.1029/2012GL051012>

⁶ Akhoudas et al. (2020) - <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019JC015710>

⁷ England et al. (2020) - DOI: 10.1126/sciadv.abd1273

⁸ Wåhlin et al. (2020) - <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2014-5>

⁹ Jenkins et al. (2010) - <https://doi.org/10.1038/ngeo890>

These novel observations made under and around grounded icebergs and surrounding sea-ice on Bear Ridge will provide otherwise unobtainable in situ data for the tuning and validation of iceberg module development within NEMO and deployment in coupled ice sheet-climate modelling.

WP2 will also deploy instrumentation to measure cavity turbulence (UKRI-BAS) and oxygen isotopes (CNRS-IGE) on the Fimbul ice shelf.

In WP3, “Ice sheet mass balance, forcing and dynamics”, and in WP11, “Atmosphere and ocean dynamics”, OCEAN ICE will provide updated values and uncertainties for freshwater fluxes from the AIS to the ocean over the satellite observational period to the present day, including surface melt and runoff, ice flow, basal melt and calving. Moreover, OCEAN ICE will quantify freshwater flux from solid and liquid precipitation in the Antarctic Peninsula, assess the ocean circulation beneath ice shelves in the Weddell Sea and the impact of breaking waves on ice melt rates.

WP3 will include the following:

- EO: Contribution of continental-scale ice dynamics processes to freshwater fluxes.
 - a) Produce a comprehensive EO dataset of AIS freshwater fluxes, including calving fluxes, basal melt (ApRES) and EO surface melt rates.
- Contribution of surface mass budget and ice shelf processes:
 - a) Produce RCM surface fluxes accounting for wind-blown snow, firn densification and saturation and basal ice shelf melt;
 - b) Assimilation of SMB and basal melt into a hindcast covering the whole AIS to initialise ice sheet models and identify atmospheric variability impacts on ice sheet mass budget.
- Subglacial fresh-water discharge from the AIS into the Southern Ocean:
 - a) Compute buoyancy plume-driven melt and subglacial discharge contribution to ice shelves computed using state-of-the-art surface-to-bed inversions and a subglacial hydrological model to provide the first estimates of water fluxes across all grounding lines on a continental-wide basis.
- Developing methodologies for hindcasting from ice-sheet models:
 - a) Using a regional coupled model and applying the IEnKS initialisation algorithm for initialising coupled ice-ocean models, idealised domains and synthetic observations will be used to provide a proof of concept, and a realistic regional Amundsen Sea initialisation.
 - b) Apply ensemble-based assimilation to choose the initial state and parameters of the ice sheet-ocean model, minimising mismatch and drift.

WP11 will include the following:

- Historical evaluation:
 - a) Assess the importance of rain and snow precipitation in the Southern Ocean and the occurrence of extreme events over the Antarctic Peninsula region using high-resolution climate downscaling.
- Particle tracking:
 - a) Modelling of Weddell Sea circulation using particle tracking to determine float placement pre-fieldwork and to analyse and verify model simulations with float data;
 - b) Assessment of the importance of internal waves on ice melt rates.
- PolarWRF Modelling:

- a) High-resolution PolarWRF simulations (9-3-1km) with two-moment microphysics parameterisations to compare with the observations of precipitation during extreme events.

WP3 produces a comprehensive EO dataset of AIS freshwater fluxes, including calving fluxes, basal melt (ApRES) and EO surface melt rates. Existing ApRES (in situ phase-sensitive radar time series of ice shelf thickness at ~1 mm precision) datasets will be consolidated and integrated with other open AWS observational datasets, shallow ice cores and snow stake measurements into a comprehensive model evaluation dataset. ApRES observations will also be used as an independent evaluation of snowfall accumulation rates from RCMs and satellite-derived basal melt rates over ice shelves. These are sensitive to model physics in RCM and are some of the most significant uncertainties currently associated with mass budget estimates in Antarctica. WP3 uses state-of-the-art models, while the above approach represents a considerable community advance for assessing model uncertainties.

In WP4, “Quantification of Antarctic Ice Sheet ‘deep uncertainty’, OCEAN ICE utilises improved initialisation states from WP3 to project the freshwater fluxes of the AIS in ice sheet and coupled ice sheet-ocean models from 2020 to 2300 and its contribution to SLR. More specifically, it does:

- Model initialisation and initial sensitivity analysis.
 - a) Apply optimisation techniques and data on bedrock elevation, ice thickness, ice thickness changes, surface velocity, surface mass balance and ice shelf basal to estimate the present-day state of the AIS employing the f.ETISh model (ULB) and the Úa model (UNN).
 - b) Assess the spread in AIS fluxes for a range of uncertain glaciological processes.
- Surrogate modelling and UQ in Antarctic ice sheet models.
 - a) A large ensemble of 300-year-long simulations will be carried out with f.ETISh and Úa, each covering the whole space of uncertain physical parameters and uncertain climate forcing.
 - b) Train multi-output surrogate models for calving, basal melt, surface runoff and the grounding line fluxes. Stochastic analysis of model uncertainties and a complete sensitivity analysis for all Antarctic drainage basins.
- Benchmarking against high-resolution coupled ice-ocean simulations.
 - a) High-resolution simulations of the coupled ÚaMITgcm for Amundsen and Weddell Sea drainage basins. 300-year simulations for an ‘optimal’ range of model parameters and forcings, to capture AIS sensitivity.
 - b) Further develop ÚaMITgcm configurations to include moving ice fronts and surface runoff. Coupled ice-ocean response compared to ice sheet only simulations, and feedbacks are analysed.

In WP5, “Ice sheet impacts on global ocean circulation”, OCEAN ICE examines the impact of ice sheet meltwater discharge on deep water formation and export from the poles, and the ultimate impact upon large-scale ocean circulation, including the AMOC and ACC. More specifically, it considers:

- Bottom water transport and properties:
 - a) Installation of an AABW physics monitoring mooring array in the South Sandwich Trench.

- b) It will make the first sustained mooring observation of the primary AABW pathway from the Weddell Sea to the global ocean.
- c) Determine AABW transport, properties and variability, linked to contemporaneous mooring observations in Orkney Passage and elsewhere in the Weddell Sea, EO and reanalysis wind data, and model output.
- d) Supplement the SAMBA array with AABW monitoring instrumentation.
- e) Examine the AABW salinity and transport variability in the context of upstream water mass properties, freshwater inputs and SAMBA.
- f) AABW contribution to AMOC via new instrument deployments in the SAMBA array
- North-South freshwater impacts on ocean circulation up to millennial timescales.
 - a) Global hydrographic data, including water isotopes, inversion to reconstruct surface boundary conditions on decadal to (multi) centennial timescales.
 - b) Reconstruction of surface oxygen isotope ratios, and meteoric water/sea-ice impact on dense water properties.
 - c) NEMO simulations up to 3,000 years forced with increased ice mass loss in Antarctica and Greenland scenarios. NorESM (coupled Greenland ice sheet) decadal IPCC-SSP climate scenario simulations. Both simulations assess the impact of increased glacial melting on global ocean circulation, including its effects on the AMOC, ACC, upper-ocean gyres, and southern and northern deep-water formation.

An array of three moorings (provided by UKRI-BAS, logistics by South African DFFE) will be deployed across the unobserved main AABW flow path from the Weddell Sea, across the ridge crossing the southern part of the South Sandwich Trench, measuring temperature, salinity, pressure and velocity. A two-year deployment will allow the first estimates of total Weddell Sea AABW export properties and variability. This will be concurrent with the existing UKRI-BAS Orkney Passage array, the other primary AABW pathway, enabling direct comparisons of magnitude and co-variability, and potential reconstruction of past export.

To link this work to the global circulation and understand the basin-scale impact of AABW heat and freshwater content change ⁽¹⁰⁾, OCEAN ICE will establish the first continuous cross-basin monitoring of AABW properties in the South Atlantic. The deeper layer of the SAMBA array will be equipped with new sensors by SAMOC partners. Microcats measuring temperature, salinity and pressure will be added to each of eight existing ENS-LMD partnered moorings (by Brazil and South Africa SAMOC partners in 2023/2025). They will allow the first high temporal resolution observations of AABW properties across the South Atlantic.

WP5 will also provide a global context for the impact of high-latitude deep water formation on global ocean properties and circulation. It will use the interior distribution of water mass properties derived from existing global salinity and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ hydrography to make a novel application of an inverse approach ⁽¹¹⁾.

This will reconstruct surface boundary conditions on decadal timescales and, for older deep waters, extend the relevant surface boundary condition to (multi) centennial timescales.

This study will include an analysis of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ decorrelation length and time scales and will provide information that can be used to inform (e.g. via SOOS) new high latitude $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ sampling strategies.

¹⁰ Purkey and Johnson (2010) - <https://doi.org/10.1175/2010JCLI3682>.

¹¹ Gabby and Huybers (2012) - <https://doi.org/10.1175/JPO-D-11-043.1>.

The inverse analysis itself will produce a unique observation-based historical time series of surface oxygen isotope ratios. This will inform WP2 isotope modelling and can be used to inform the magnitude and likely range of variability in boundary conditions, in addition to identifying historical variability and extreme events.

In WP6, “Role of Antarctica in the global climate (long-term impacts of short-term decision-making)”, OCEAN ICE will quantify the impact of changes in the freshwater fluxes, including icebergs, from Antarctica on the global climate system.

- Freshwater and iceberg fluxes forcing the global ocean
 - a) determine the fate and local impacts of future fluxes of icebergs and freshwater leaving the Antarctic ice sheet.
 - b) Coupled Southern Ocean NEMO BISICLES simulations of the recent past will be used to validate the iceberg circulation model and freshwater input by the historical ice sheet.
 - c) Projections up to 2300 will examine the impact of freshwater fluxes on large-scale ocean circulation. Freshwater feedbacks onto the coupled ice sheet evolution will be emphasised and higher resolution complements Task 6.2 (D6.1).
- Earth system impacts to 2300.
 - a) Assess the global impacts and feedback of enhanced polar freshwater and iceberg calving (WP2) on future climate using the UKESM coupled with interactive Greenland and Antarctica ice sheets.
 - b) Simulations up to 2300 using the extended socio-economic pathways (SSP) and including scenarios developed in WP4 covering the full range of high-end uncertainties.
 - c) An assessment of the impacts of enhanced freshwater and iceberg calving on a range of global and regional climate indices (Section 1.2.4.3) and implications for global tipping points (D6.2).
- Millennial-scale impacts and potential for tipping cascades.
 - a) Centennial runs forced by RCM output and millennial scale coupled PISM-MOM will be used to assess the risk of crossing critical thresholds in atmospheric and oceanic drivers of the ice-sheet dynamics and (rate of) ice loss (Section 1.2.4.3) (D6.3). Model development and analysis contribute to TIPMIP planning and implementation.

3.3 Data types and data formats

As anticipated, OCEAN ICE is planning an ambitious set of quasi-simultaneous circumpolar observations to observe the pathways, properties and high-resolution variability of water masses associated with Antarctic ice-ocean interaction over periods of several years.

Fig. 3: In situ methodology.

Fig. 4: In situ and OCEAN ICE activities.

These in situ observations include mostly delayed-mode data and some operational data.

OCEAN ICE members and partners operate existing mooring arrays in the Amundsen Sea (UKRI-BAS), eastern (KOPRI) and western Ross Sea (NIWA). These data will be complemented with current, hydrographic and bottom pressure sensors to allow intercomparison between various datasets and identify propagating signals. The ensemble will provide a circumpolar wave time series covering the 2020-2024 time period (and 2009-present in the Amundsen Sea). Upstream fluxes, in front of and under the Filchner ice shelf, will be reconstructed from moored time series combined with virtual moorings (where data is lacking).

Fig. 5: New planned in situ observation (2023/2024) - OI is OCEAN ICE.

OCEAN ICE will deploy three pairs of ice-capable floats in regions that are currently poorly observed and represent important links between areas of significant ice-ocean interaction. One pair will be deployed between the Amundsen and the Ross Sea (KOPRI supported), to connect upstream and downstream moored arrays and the other two pairs along the East Antarctic margin near the Denman Glacier (AAPP/GEOMAR), and the Totten Ice Shelf (JARE).

A Hugin autonomous underwater vehicle (AUV) operated by UGOT (deployed by KOPRI, 2022/23 season) will be used to *acquire new hydrographic and bathymetric data from the ice shelf cavities of Thwaites, Dotson, and/or Pine Island Glaciers, as well as the iceberg 'graveyard' on Bear Ridge.*

Fig. 6: AUV missions to collect high-resolution (1 dm) maps of icebase, high-resolution (<5 dm) maps of seabed, T, S and O₂, CO₂, nitrate, FI, turbidity, watersamples(150 ml each), and current velocity.

Fig. 7: UAV mission (from top).

Cool ice shelf observations will be made through boreholes on the Fimbul Ice Shelf (2023/24 season). Two OCEAN ICE instruments will be deployed within the ice shelf cavity.

Fig. 8: Fimbul Ice Shelf Observatory.

Firstly, a novel instrument developed at CNRS, providing continuous measurement of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ water isotope ratios, will be deployed in the Antarctic for the first time. This will give a new method for determining mixing, melting, and refreezing across the ocean boundary layer beneath the ice shelf, thereby expanding recent applications of this novel tracer within the region. Secondly, three UKRI-BAS turbulence instrument clusters (TICs) will be deployed across a basal channel: one at the channel centre, one on the channel flank, and one outside the channel extent. This yearlong deployment will measure basal melt rates and resolve the turbulent scalar and momentum fluxes in the ice shelf-ocean boundary layer responsible for driving basal melting.

OCEAN ICE observations will be complemented by contemporaneous NPI observations of the cavity hydrography and helium isotopes. Together, these observations will elucidate the mixing and turbulent dynamics of the ice shelf-ocean boundary layer and impacts on basal melting.

An array of four moorings (three already provided by UKRI-BAS, logistics by South African DFFE) will be deployed across the unobserved main AABW flow path from the Weddell Sea, immediately south of the South Sandwich Trench, measuring temperature, salinity, pressure and velocity.

Fig. 9: AABW properties. [2022/2023] Cruise DY158: Krill work near South Georgia, A23 section repeat, M2 mooring recovery and turnaround, circuit of A76-A iceberg, 6 mooring recovered + 4 redeployed; RRS Sir David Attenborough: M3 mooring recovery and redeployment. [2023/2024 plan] working with the fishing company instead of SA Agulhas II. [2024/2025 plan] Mooring cruise to Orkney Passage/M2/M3 on RRS Sir David Attenborough through BIOPOLE.

OCEAN ICE is establishing the first continuous cross-basin monitoring of AABW properties in the South Atlantic by instrumenting the deepest layer of the existing SAMBA array, across the Atlantic at 34.5°S. Microcats measuring temperature, salinity and pressure will be added to each of eight existing ENS-LMD partnered moorings (by Brazil and South Africa SAMOC partners in 2023/2025). Two automatic weather stations (AWS) will be operated on the Larsen C ice shelf (UU). In addition, existing ApRES (in situ phase-sensitive radar time series of ice shelf thickness at ~1 mm precision) datasets will be consolidated and integrated with other open AWS observational datasets, shallow ice cores and snow stake measurements into a comprehensive model evaluation dataset.

This in situ data will be complemented with remote sensing/satellite data from major European Earth Observation programs and agencies (e.g. Copernicus, ICESat-2, SMOS, ESA, etc.)

3.4 Data utility outside the project

OCEAN ICE's goals necessitate explicit scientific and logistical collaboration with numerous national and international research bodies. SCAR, SOOS, IASC, APECS, and SIOS are a high-level, not exhaustive list of these bodies. In turn, all these bodies will benefit from the OCEAN ICE activities and outcomes.

OCEAN ICE directly combines and dramatically extends the expertise, development and findings of three existing H2020 programmes and EU Polar Cluster Members: PROTECT (G. Durand), TIPACCs (P. Langebroek/S. Østerhus) and SO-CHIC (J.-B. Sallee). These projects, respectively, examine the cryosphere's contributions to SLR, AIS stability, and the role of the Southern Ocean in the global climate. OCEAN ICE combines these foci into a coherent view of the role of AIS freshwater flux within the global climate. It includes the coordinators, numerous WP leads and other members of these projects. OCEAN ICE has been carefully constructed to complement, combine and extend these projects. It also links with PolarRES (R. Mottram), and output from PolarRES will supplement WP3 with regional climate simulations for both present and future scenarios.

Additionally, it will benefit from and contribute to the development of ice sheet-climate coupled model improvements (including UKESM) undertaken in the H2020 project ESM2025, via WP2 co-lead N. Jourdain and WP3 co-lead G. Durand. WP9 UKRI-BAS is a WP co-lead in ARCTIC PASSION and provides a link between the Sustaining Arctic Observing Network (SAON) and the OCEAN ICE analysis of Greenland Ice Sheet stability (WP5/6). WP2 and WP6 of OCEAN ICE will make significant developmental contributions to core European community modelling efforts, including NEMO and UKESM, and will partner closely with these consortia. Links to ecosystem research are provided through collaboration with UK BIOPOLE (A. Meijers, M. Meredith). OCEAN ICE member EPB leads policy and communications work in SO-CHIC and INTERACT III, and legacy planning and implementation in EU-PolarNet 2 and its planned European Polar Coordination Office (EPCO). It will ensure impactful connections and collaborations are made with these and other EU Polar Cluster members.

Clear collaborative opportunities have been identified: Combined AMOC assessment at the SAMBA array (e.g. EPOC WP1, WP5 member S. Speich is a member of AMOC-ASAP); Greenland Ice Sheet and southern freshwater pathways (WP1/5 member A. Naveira Garabato is WP3 lead of AMOC-NEXT); reconstruction of the recent past AMOC water masses (WP5 co-lead E. McDonagh is a member of AMOC-NEXT) and WP5-6 identification of AMOC response to freshwater forcing aligns with EPOC WP4.

OCEAN ICE directly contributes instrumentation and scientific collaboration to the SAMBA project (WP5, S. Speich) through the Brazilian SAMBAR project/Vema channel array (partner E. Campos) and South African DFFE (partner T. Lamont). Data will be collaborated on with the SAMOC project (partner A. Piola) and will contribute to the AtlantOS, AANCHOR and the implementation of the All-Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance. It also links to the RAPID array, TRIATLAS and ABC fluxes Atlantic projects via E. McDonagh (WP5 co-lead). Moreover a strong scientific network is established with South Korea KOPRI (partner W. Sang) for deployments of WP2 AUV and WP1 moorings/floats; New Zealand NIWA (partner C. Stevens) for Ross Sea moorings/floats (WP1); Australian AAPP (partner N. Bindoff) for Denman Glacier float deployments (WP1); Japanese JARE/HEAT-CROSS (partner S. Aoki) for Totten glacier float deployments (WP1); German GEOMAR (partner M. Gutjahr) east Antarctic/Americe ice shelf float deployments (WP1), with floats potentially sourced from German BSH (partner B. Klein); Norway NPI (partner/WP1 member T. Hattermann) hot water drilling and borehole access on Fimbul Ice Shelf (WP2) and the South African DFFE (partner T. Lamont) supporting deployment of South Sandwich Trench moorings (WP5). Scientific collaboration and data sharing will be conducted with all partners.

OCEAN ICE will contribute to the UN Decade on Ocean Science, through EPB's membership of the Task Group leading the process, and chair roles in working groups (R. Badhe, S. Speich), the Southern Ocean Observing System through steering committee or working groups (A. Meijers, J-B. Sallee, M. Janout, P. Dutrieux, M. Meredith), GOOS and associated GO-SHIP initiative, through steering committees (E. McDonagh), ITGC and the NECKLACE programme, through A. Wåhlin and K. Nicholls.

Reduced uncertainties in polar impacts on global climate, including SLR: A core objective of OCEAN ICE is to reduce the uncertainty in future projections of SLR and climate impacts due to changes in the Antarctic and Greenland Ice Sheets. WP5-6 will produce these results, and they will be expected to inform and be cited within IPCC and WOA Assessment Reports and, as such, influence the UNFCCC processes. These will primarily be presented through the reports/chapters dealing with the cryosphere, oceans, climate/SLR, and adaptation. This expectation is supported by the prominent role

as co-ordinating lead, lead and contributing authors that numerous OCEAN ICE members have played in these chapters in previous assessment reports, including the most recent AR6 and the Special Report on the Ocean and Cryosphere in a Changing Climate. Additional exploitation of results will be achieved through scientific and steering contributions to the premier model intercomparison projects (CMIP, ISMIP6/7, MISOMIP2) that underpin future projections and uncertainty.

Direct improvements to key European and global community ESMs: OCEAN ICE will improve and further develop several important community ice sheets, oceans and climate models. Improvements to the NEMO iceberg, sea-ice and isotope modules (WP2) will be adopted into the model ‘trunk’, providing long-term support and integration into future developments. This ocean model serves as the basis for several EU coupled climate models, including UKESM, which WP5 and WP6 will utilise to validate the improvements in coupled setups. The focus within OCEAN ICE on coupling between the wider climate and ice sheets is also recognised as a critically needed next step in climate model development, so community interest and uptake of OCEAN ICE model development and results is expected to be high. Advances in glacial freshwater integration in NorESM (WP5) will benefit the planned future development of a fully coupled ice sheet-NorESM. Finally, NEMO and other models employed (BISICLES, f.ETISH and Elmer/Ice, etc.) are open source and form the basis for many coupled ice sheet-ocean and ESMs globally. Thus, it is expected that project model development will propagate far beyond the OCEAN ICE community.

Support of key operational and reanalysis data products: OCEAN ICE targets critical gaps in our observational network of the ocean, particularly around the ice-threatened Antarctic coastline, under ice shelves and icebergs and in the deep ocean abyss. These data (WP1-3/5) will be quality-controlled, processed, and propagated (WP7) in a delayed mode to the European open-access repositories (e.g., CMEMS, EMODnet), which are responsible for providing data to historical reconstructions (reanalysis) datasets (e.g., ERAint) and climatologies (EN4). Instruments providing near real-time data (e.g. floats deployed for the German Argo initiative) will also provide information in these data deserts to support operational weather and sea-ice forecasting models (e.g. from ECMWF) that feed through to services such as the Copernicus Maritime Surveillance Service that support operations from fisheries to maritime safety.

Improved coordination between ocean and ice modelling, observational and EO communities: OCEAN ICE recognises the need for greater coordination between the polar in situ, EO and modelling communities to tackle the deeply coupled problem of polar impacts on climate.

Coordination and dissemination of observations from new and emerging technologies: OCEAN ICE exploits novel and emerging polar observing platforms, including ice-avoiding profiling floats in bottom landing mode, AUV instrumentation, experimental isotope and mixing instrumentation deployed through ice boreholes, and ice-penetrating radar (ApRES). There is a recognised need to bring together these disparate datasets, often only held by individual research teams, into more integrated data delivery platforms. In collaboration with OCEAN ICE (WP7,8), SOOS will coordinate a workshop (2024/2025) on the standardisation, harmonisation and sharing of such datasets.

Improved long-term monitoring capability: While most OCEAN ICE observations are derived from short-term instrument deployments, the WP5 instrumentation of the SAMBA array and establishment of a deep mooring array at the South Sandwich Trench reflect a commitment to the long-term monitoring of AABW pathways and properties. These instruments will remain in place, maintained by

the SAMBA array consortium and UKRI-BAS respectively, beyond the lifetime of OCEAN ICE. They will provide an OCEAN ICE legacy to continue monitoring the multi-decadal decline in AABW volume as it spreads north to form part of the lower overturning cell in the AMOC.

3.5 SOOS Data Guidelines

Considering one OCEANICE key stakeholder is SOOS, OCEANICE adopts and promotes the SOOS Data Guideline and EMODnet recommendations for standards and vocabularies.

3.5.1 Purpose

The Southern Ocean Observing System (SOOS) Data Guidelines outline the requirements for data inclusion in SOOSmap, promoting consistency, accessibility, and interoperability. SOOSmap serves as a publicly accessible geospatial data platform supporting interdisciplinary research in the Southern Ocean. These guidelines outline best practices for data submission, formatting, metadata requirements, and geospatial criteria to facilitate open and standardised data sharing, ensuring that data adheres to the [FAIR principles](#) (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability).

3.5.2 Scope

1. SOOSmap will only provide access to and make publicly available data. SOOSmap does not have the capacity to host private, limited-access data (e.g., sensitive data or Personally Identifiable Information, PII).
2. SOOSmap provides access to observational scientific data; experimental or modelled data are not within the scope of SOOSmap.
3. SOOSmap supports data across all scientific disciplines, including physical, biological, chemical and meteorological data.

3.5.3 Data Formats and Structure

1. Data must be within an open-source, standardised format (e.g., CSV, JSON, NetCDF). For data to be accessible and visible via SOOSmap, they must not be in proprietary formats requiring specific software to read (e.g., SAS7BDAT for statistical software SAS) or in non-machine-readable formats (e.g., PDFs).
2. Data variables must be identifiable and categorised into one of the following:
 - a. String or Text.
 - b. Numerical (i.e., discrete, or continuous).
 - c. Date or Datetime.
 - d. Geometry (i.e., point, line, polygon).
3. Standardised terminologies and vocabularies should be utilised, where possible, to improve the interoperability of the data. For example, [NERC Vocabulary Server \(NVS\) terminologies](#), or [NetCDF Climate and Forecast \(CF\) standard names](#).
4. Use text labels and URIs to identify terms coming from controlled vocabularies (e.g. parameter and parameter_URI).

3.5.4 Geospatial Requirements

1. While SOOSmap has the capacity to provide access to many global datasets, the focus of SOOSmap is data that fall within the geographic coverage of the Southern Ocean. This, in

turn, is defined as the waters covered by the [SOOS Regional Working Groups map](#). Broadly, the SOOS Regions cover waters south of 50°S, though the northern boundary varies between regions.

2. Data must be georeferenced and have a datetime to be accessible and visible within SOOSmap. Therefore, data must contain coordinates (e.g., Latitude and Longitude), or a geometry (e.g., point, line, polygon).
3. Data must also contain a Coordinate Reference System (CRS) and time (ISO 8061) to enable accurate mapping.

3.5.5 Data Storage and Metadata

1. SOOSmap does not have the capacity to host data or act as a data storage option. Observational data within SOOSmap are preferably hosted in a community-approved external data repository (e.g., UK Polar Data Centre, Australia Antarctic Data Centre, etc.).
 - a. If a suitable repository for the data is not known, SOOS can help identify the most appropriate national or international repository or data aggregator.
2. An external metadata record describing the data must exist, so that SOOSmap can link to and harvest the following:
 - a. Dataset Title.
 - b. Data publisher/owner.
 - c. Abstract and details on the methodology surrounding the collection and description of the data.
 - d. Data update frequency (e.g., never, daily, yearly).
 - e. Digital Object Identifier (DOI) for the metadata/data, including a permalink for continued data access.
 - f. Any licensing/limitations for publishing or using the data.

Data license: SOOSmap endorses the principle that data should be “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”. In general, SOOSmap recommends and welcomes CC0 for metadata and CC-BY for data.

3.5.6 Quality Control and Validation

1. Data must undergo quality control checks before submission and inclusion in SOOSmap. This includes, but is not limited to:
 - a. Ensuring datetimes are provided in a proper and consistent format (e.g., ISO 8601 "YYYY-MM-DD").
 - b. Ensuring coordinates are all in the same format (e.g., decimal degrees) across the data.
 - c. Outliers and missing values should be documented and handled appropriately.
 - d. Numerical variables contain only numeric values.
 - e. Units are provided and standardised (e.g., [The Unified Code for Units of Measure, UCUM](#)), where required.
2. Data processing steps and known limitations should be clearly stated in the metadata (metadata should include links - URIs - to applied/applicable best practice).

4. FAIR data

The objectives of the OCEAN ICE project are intrinsically linked to the achievement of long-term scientific and societal outcomes. By improving the representation of ocean–ice interactions in Earth System Models (ESMs) and supporting the development of reliable climate services, the project contributes to more accurate projections of sea ice loss, sea level rise, ocean heat uptake, and extreme events. These efforts are closely aligned with international frameworks (e.g., CMIP7, GCOS, GOOS) and European priorities in sustainable ocean management and climate adaptation.

In this context, **adherence to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles** (Wilkinson et al., 2016) is essential to ensure that OCEAN ICE research outputs are widely usable, transparent, and machine-actionable. The FAIR framework provides clear guidance for data stewardship at both metadata and data levels, and it aligns with Horizon Europe open science requirements.

European programmes and projects, such as Copernicus, EMODnet, SeaDataNet, and H2020 EuroSea, have significantly contributed to advancing FAIR principles by aligning with the 15 characteristics laid down by the FORCE11 collective. Studies by Tanhua et al. (2019) and Quimbert et al. (2022) have detailed these advancements, highlighting significant progress in data standards and machine-to-machine data processing over the past three decades. These initiatives adhere to FAIR principles, providing a comprehensive framework for effective data management.

Tab. 2: FAIR principles proposed by the FORCE11 community.

Findable	
F1	(meta)data are assigned a globally unique and eternally persistent identifier.
F2	data are described with rich metadata.
F3	(meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.
F4	metadata specifies the data identifier.
Accessible	
A1	(meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol.
A1.1	the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable.
A1.2	the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary.
A2	metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available.
Interoperable	
I1	(meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
I2	(meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles.
I3	(meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data.
Re-usable	
R1	(meta)data have a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes.
R1.1	(meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license.
R1.2	(meta)data are associated with their provenance.
R1.3	(meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards.

Notably, these recommendations always include three main elements for implementing interoperability: metadata (including data quality), data format, and data services.

More specifically, according to our Grant Agreement (Art.187), metadata of deposited publications must be open under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent, in line with the FAIR principles (in particular, machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following:

- publication (author(s),
- title,
- date of publication,
- publication venue,
- Horizon Europe or Euratom funding,
- grant project name, acronym and number,
- licensing terms,
- persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant.

Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the publication.

In terms of data availability, partners will need to make their research data available as soon as possible and within the deadlines outlined in the DMP, ensuring open access.

Nevertheless, data usability strongly depends on the data policy license, and in this regard, there is an increasing push for adopting the Common Creative framework and, in particular, the CC-BY license (the only limitation is that credit must be given to the creator). Embargo of data and other CC-licences can also be applied wherever the policy is 'As open as possible, as closed as necessary'.

Partners can avoid offering open access in two cases:

- OA be against the beneficiary's legitimate interests, including regarding commercial exploitation,

or

- OA be contrary to any other constraints, in particular the EU competitive interests or the beneficiary's obligations under this Agreement; if open access is not provided (to some or all data), this must be justified in the DMP.

Any decision to withhold open access to data, in whole or in part, must be reported and justified by partners in the data management plan (more specifically under Annex 1 – Data inventory).

4.1 Requirements for OCEAN ICE FAIR data

The following table summarises how the OCEAN ICE project aligns with the FAIR principles. For each principle (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), the table lists the relevant subsections described in the data management plan and provides a concise explanation of the associated requirements and practices.

Making data Findable	Observational platform	Each in situ platform/station must have a unique ID (e.g., WMO code via OceanOPS, https://www.ocean-ops.org/).
	Institution	The institution responsible for the data must be identified via an EDMO code (SeaDataNet ¹²). See Table 8 in Appendix for EDMO codes of OCEAN ICE partners.
	Principal investigator and research team	Researchers associated with the data must have a persistent identifier (e.g., ORCID ¹³).
	Project identifier and funding	Projects must be referenced with official identifiers (e.g., CORDIS, EDMERP ¹⁴). The OCEAN ICE reference on CORDIS is: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060452 The OCEAN ICE reference on the EDMERP database: https://edmerp.seadatanet.org/report/13721
	Dataset identifier	Datasets must have persistent DOIs (e.g., through Zenodo ¹⁵ publication); timestamps/versions must be managed to ensure traceability.
	Collect DOI and make data available	Strategy for DOI assignment and publication: near real time (interoperability via ERDDAP or FTP), delayed mode and reanalysis (request DOI from national infrastructures ¹⁶ /Zenodo/SEANOE ¹⁷ /PANGAEA ¹⁸).
Making data Accessible	Data format	Use of standard formats for interoperability: the preferred transport format for operational data is NetCDF-CF (\geq v1.6), also HDF ¹⁹ .
	Metadata	Metadata must comply with ISO 19115 ²⁰ , ISO 8601 (date and time), SeaDataNet (NVS POx description of parameters), CF conventions (parameters standard names), WGS84 (datum). Use of controlled vocabularies is mandatory (see Table 9 in the Appendix).

¹² <https://edmo.seadatanet.org/results>

¹³ Information and registration: <https://orcid.org/>

¹⁴ <https://www.seadatanet.org/Metadata/EDMERP-Projects>

¹⁵ <https://help.zenodo.org/>

¹⁶ e.g. in France, IFREMER can assign DOI; in Italy, INGV; in Germany, PANAGEA, etc.

¹⁷ <https://www.seanoe.org/html/doi-complementarity-with-databases.htm>

¹⁸ <https://www.pangaea.de/>

¹⁹ <https://www.hdfgroup.org/solutions/hdf5/>

²⁰ <https://www.iso.org/standard/53798.html>

	Use of uncommon or unavailable ontologies or vocabularies	When new terms are required, interact with NVS/SeaDataNet for community definition and adoption. A GitHub repository for key NVS vocabularies tracks the discussion on new terms adoption ²¹ .
	INSPIRE	EU Directive for sharing spatial environmental data, with specifications (EF, OF, O&M data models) ensuring interoperability across EU member states.
Making data Interoperable	Data services	Use of standard open-source tools for interoperability: ERDDAP ²² (marine data server), GeoNetwork (metadata catalogue), GeoServer (vector data/maps management).
	Data infrastructure	Backend based on Docker (CentOS VM, 32GB RAM, 500GB), modular architecture with access controlled via IP/FQDN whitelist.
	Delivering data to (trusted) infrastructure	Integration with European infrastructures (Copernicus, EMODnet, Euro-Argo, ICOS, SeaDataNet) and automatic connection to EOSC.
Making data Reusable	Data description and documentation	Extended documentation including metadata, algorithms, workflows, models, and software.
	Data traceability	Traceability of data and products through DOIs, citations, and references.
	Data license	Use of open licences (preferably CC ²³ , CC-BY). Embargo (6–24 months) may apply, but metadata must always remain open.

4.2. Data Quality principles

4.2.1 Research Integrity and Scientific Quality

OCEAN ICE recognises that high-quality science relies on the integrity of the research process. All researchers involved in the project are expected to uphold the highest professional and ethical standards, ensuring that data, methods, and results are trustworthy, transparent, and reproducible. The following principles guide the work of OCEAN ICE at every stage of the research lifecycle:

²¹ github.com/nvs-vocabs

²² <https://coastwatch.pfeg.noaa.gov/erddap/index.html>

²³ Refer to <https://creativecommons.org/about/cclicenses/> for all detailed information on CC licences.

Academic Excellence

Research activities must apply sound methodologies, robust experimental and modelling techniques, and, where appropriate, internationally recognised procedures and documented protocols. This ensures that results are reliable, disseminated through proper channels, and reproducible by the broader scientific community.

Honesty

Scientific outputs must accurately reflect the research conducted. Researchers are required to acknowledge both direct and indirect contributions from colleagues, collaborators and external sources. Honesty applies not only to the presentation of one's own work but also to interactions with the broader scientific community.

Accountability

Researchers bear responsibility to the public, to funding bodies, and to the scientific community. They must ensure compliance with project agreements, institutional policies and relevant professional codes of conduct. Transparency and traceability are integral to this accountability, including the documentation of data provenance, processing steps, and governance structures.

Care and respect

Research must be conducted with due consideration for the safety, rights, and dignity of individuals, communities, and the environment. OCEAN ICE researchers will take all reasonable measures to avoid harm or undue risk to research participants, colleagues, and the marine and polar environments in which data are collected.

4.2.2. Data Quality Assurance

In addition to integrity principles, OCEAN ICE adopts a structured approach to ensure that all project data meets the highest quality standards. The project aligns with the EU Data Quality Guidelines and implements best practices in open science and FAIR data management.

Key measures include:

- **FAIR-compliant data management**
All datasets will be made Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable, supported by the use of persistent identifiers (DOIs), rich metadata and open licensing.
- **Standardised formats and models**
Data will be stored and disseminated in widely adopted community formats (e.g. NetCDF/CF for environmental data, CSV for tabular data, GeoTIFF for spatial layers), ensuring compatibility with scientific and operational systems.
- **Controlled vocabularies and ontologies**
Common dictionaries and controlled vocabularies (ISO standards, SeaDataNet, BODC, GCMD keywords, CF Standard Names) will be applied to guarantee semantic consistency and interoperability.
- **Robust infrastructures**
Data will be hosted in backend systems that support multiple formats, conversion tools, and long-term preservation, ensuring both flexibility and sustainability.
- **Transparent methodology**
Every dataset will document the applied scientific methods, protocols, and quality control

procedures, with references to peer-reviewed literature or recognised best practices. This ensures reproducibility and facilitates integration with other datasets.

- **Linked quality control procedures**

As quality control processes vary by platform and data type (e.g. in situ observations, satellite data, model outputs), OCEAN ICE metadata will include explicit links to the applied validation protocols and relevant best practices from the **Ocean Best Practices System (OBPS)** and European Commission standards.

5. Open Science

Open Science is a global movement that seeks to make every stage of the research process as transparent, accessible, and reusable as possible, fostering more collaborative, inclusive and impactful science. It spans the entire research lifecycle, from project design through data collection, analysis, and dissemination, by emphasising openness and accessibility at each step. As outlined in the *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science* (2021), its core goals include strengthening scientific collaboration, enhancing reproducibility, and ensuring that scientific knowledge benefits both research communities and society at large.

A central element of Open Science is the creation and use of digital infrastructures that enable data sharing, long-term preservation, and discoverability of research outputs. These infrastructures include both domain-specific and general-purpose repositories, as well as collaborative platforms such as the Open Science Framework (OSF), which supports version-controlled project management, documentation, and team-based data sharing. Open Science also relies on Open Access publishing, which makes articles, datasets, software, and protocols freely available without subscription barriers, thereby boosting their visibility, reuse, and citation impact.

5.1 CORDIS

The European Commission's primary platform for supporting Open Science is CORDIS (Community Research and Development Information Service), which catalogues and disseminates information about all EU-funded research projects. Through CORDIS, users can access digital outputs from these projects, which are also interconnected with the OpenAIRE system, a key pillar in the implementation of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). OpenAIRE fosters open scholarship by enhancing the discoverability, accessibility, shareability, reusability, reproducibility and monitoring of data-driven research results worldwide.

Ensuring that project outcomes are correctly listed and published in CORDIS is essential for aligning with EU recommendations on Open Science. This requires that all digital outputs are correctly linked to the project's grant agreement number and made available through the OpenAIRE system. For OCEAN ICE, this means:

- All outputs (publications, deliverables, data) must reference the project's Grant Agreement number (**101060452**), ensuring proper attribution and enabling automated harvesting by CORDIS.
- Once indexed, results appear on the official OCEAN ICE project page on CORDIS, which increases the reach and impact of the project across the scientific community and for policymakers.

- Persistent identifiers (DOIs) linked to the grant number guarantee that outputs are correctly tracked, contributing to open science reporting obligations under Horizon Europe.

CORDIS – OCEAN ICE project page: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060452>

With its Zenodo community and firm adherence to data management best practices, OCEAN ICE fully meets the EU's Open Science requirements.

5.2 Open access

Open Access is a fundamental principle of Open Science, providing free and unrestricted access to research results to promote transparency, collaboration and the sharing of knowledge.

OCEAN ICE is committed to Open Access and is among the adopters of the EU Open Research Repository Pilot. This designation enables the project to maintain a curated repository within Zenodo, directly supporting the EU's Open Science policy.

Zenodo

OCEAN ICE has established a dedicated Zenodo community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/oceanice/>) to catalogue and disseminate project outputs. Zenodo, developed by CERN and supported by OpenAIRE, ensures compliance with EU open-access policies by assigning persistent DOIs, supporting open licensing (CC-BY 4.0), and providing long-term storage of datasets, publications, and other materials.

Zenodo is used in OCEAN ICE to:

1. Provide automatic DOI assignment to datasets, deliverables, and presentations, ensuring retrievability and citability.
2. Ensure open access in compliance with the EC Grant Agreement, with metadata deposited under CC0 licences.
3. Tag outputs with the OCEAN ICE grant number (**101060452**), which allows automatic harvesting by the EC Participant Portal and subsequent display on CORDIS.
4. Guarantee long-term preservation of project outputs, with up to 200 GB of storage per item allocated to the community.

Types of materials deposited in Zenodo:

- public deliverables, presentations, posters, proceedings, factsheets, outreach material, and (where appropriate) datasets.
- All records are curated by the Data Manager to ensure metadata completeness, licence clarity, and compliance with FAIR.

Exclusions: peer-reviewed articles (unless publisher policy permits), confidential deliverables, and internal progress reports, which are handled via SharePoint or the EC Participant Portal.

To facilitate compliance, OCEAN ICE developed a dedicated section in the Project Handbook with step-by-step guidance on publishing in the Zenodo community.

6. Impact

6.1 Contribution to the project objectives

The OCEAN ICE DMP is setting the schemes and rules for project data management and sharing. More specifically is a pillar for the implementation of the:

O7: Deliver free and open data access and contribute to international assessments, climate model development, observing initiatives and policymakers.

As described in the previous section, OCEAN ICE is setting up a data management infrastructure that is adopting and adapting the recommendations and lessons learnt from major European Marine Data initiatives and is interoperable towards both EMODnet and Copernicus Marine Service. It applies FAIR principles and implements tools to be INSPIRE compliant. One key goal of OCEAN ICE is to support, further develop and empower the *SOOSmap* data system.

6.2 Contribution to the Expected Outcomes

The DMP is supporting the OCEAN ICE data management towards all its EOs.

Policy relevance

OCEAN ICE Data Management Plan is setting (proposing) a better and clearer schema for data delivery and Commission assessment on the Horizon Europe project data FAIRness, more specifically, is embracing and promoting the adoption of CC and, in particular, CC-BY whenever possible. It proposes to have clear statements on embargoed data, meaning that some data may be embargoed for enabling scientific processing and fine-tuning (and publication). However, the project is now declaring that all data will be available and linkable. New data (observational capacity) is already stated, and at the end of the project, it can be easily tracked if and how much the project was compliant with this statement.

Being in contact – cooperating with the foremost European Marine Data Integrators (EMODnet and Copernicus Marine Service) is essential to have a further channel to make value of the project data. Some OCEAN ICE data may not be included in these integrators (because of the scope, type ...). Still, it is essential that those who are of interest to these initiatives can easily interact with and interoperate with them. The adoption of open data sharing tools (e.g. ERDDAP) is a further cornerstone of this process and should be encouraged as an EU policy for research projects.

7. Other research outputs

OCEAN ICE is an ambitious project, and there will be several outputs, ranging from new data and products to deliverables, to publications, to dissemination materials. These outputs are planned, and this approach matches the open science practices. This document describes the approach to data and data product management. Plans for communication strategy, deliverable quality, document management, web, and social communication are addressed in other deliverables. The reader can refer to the Project Handbook (MS28) for an easy guide/index towards all these deliverables.

The project's data and data-products are digital objects, and they will be published together with (FAIR) metadata, be assigned a digital object identifier (doi) and be available/linkable in the OCEAN ICE web portal or web data infrastructure.

All the digital outputs are included in the OCEAN ICE ZENODO community - <https://zenodo.org/deposit/new?c=oceanice>

8. Allocation of Resources

8.1 Costs before making data or other research outputs FAIR

Besides the development and hosting of the data infrastructure that enables compliance with FAIR principles, mainly allocated by the partner ETT, all the partners have allocated a dedicated budget for the promotion and dissemination activities.

8.2 Responsible for data management

Data Management is included in a dedicated project work package (WP7), and the person responsible for the data management is Antonio Novellino, who has long experience in data management, ocean data management and sharing. Following is his employment history in brief.

Antonio Novellino, PhD in Biotechnology and Bioengineering, MSc in Biomedical Engineering and certified Computer Scientist, is Smart City Market Line Manager at ETT SpA (DEDA Group) and CEO of the SINDBAD Consortium. He is also an Adjunct Professor at the University of Genoa – DISTAV. He serves on the Scientific Board of the Ligurian Cluster of Marine Technology (DLTM) and on the Board of the TRAIN Consortium for innovation in energy and transport management. An expert in FAIR data management, information systems, WebGIS, decision support systems, and data interoperability standards (OpenDAP, THREDDS, ERDDAP, etc.), he is a member of the EuroGOOS DATAMEQ group. He contributes to the Task Teams on operational oceanography data management. He is part of the EMODnet Steering Committee and Technical Working Group, co-chair of the SOOS DMSC, and serves in the DOOS DMTT and the OceanPrediction DCC. He leads data management activities within EMODnet (Physics, Ingestion, Chemistry) and across several European projects (Copernicus Marine Service, POLARIN, OCEAN ICE, EFFECTIVE, OLAMUR, SO-CHIC, NAUTILUS, BlueCloud2026, AtlantOS, SeaDataCloud, EuroSEA, Jerico S3). He is a co-author of scientific publications and serves as a reviewer for journals and scientific initiatives.

Whenever an OCEAN ICE data product is hosted, safely kept in any other well-known/TRUST repository, WP7 will list the proper links.

8.3 Long-term preservation

The primary repository for new data is the responsible institute (e.g., BAS) or network (e.g., ARGO GDAC), which itself or is cooperating with trusted infrastructure for long-term data stewardship (e.g., PANGAEA). Moreover, OCEANICE adopted Zenodo as a further repository for the digital objects. OCEANICE also stores newly recorded in situ data into its data management infrastructure, which supports the SOOSmap and cooperates with the European Marine Observation and Data network

(the EU in situ marine data integrator). This amplifies the legacy and overall FAIRness of OCEANICE data.

Additionally, the Data Management Plan (DMP) and its Annex 1 – Data inventory provide an up-to-date version of the project datasets. This includes links to locate, access, interoperate, and reuse any project outcomes.

OCEAN ICE backend infrastructure will be maintained for at least 3 years after the end of the project (a longer time will be considered if there is any specific need).

9. Data Security

The infrastructure will be deployed on the ARUBA.it infrastructure. Since 2015, Aruba has been offering a dedicated service to private business clients, providing them with top-level services such as Data Centres (Virtual Servers, Real Servers, hosting infrastructures), backup and Disaster Recovery, and more. ARUBA also provides us with the most recent services for data security cryptography (AES), security protocols (AES, SSL) and bandwidth balance. The main characteristics of the service are:

SLA:	99,80%
Security:	crypted transmission channel (optional) storage crypting AES-256
Min backup timing:	1h
Schedule:	anytime granularity – single backup job
Backup Account number:	unlimited
Concurrent agents:	depends on the agreed service
Max number of backup jobs:	unlimited
Bandwidth:	unlimited (upload/download)
Certifications:	ISO 9001:2015, ISO 27001:2013
Service desk:	24h
Cloud security certification:	ISO/IEC 27017:2015
Data privacy:	ISO/IEC 2018:2014
Security incidents:	ISO/IEC 27035:2016

10. Ethics and GDPR

Ethics and GDPR are covered by the OCEAN ICE Project Handbook (Milestone M28) and the deliverable D9.9 “OCEAN ICE Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion Policy (EDI)”.

11. Conclusions

This document presents the preliminary version of the OCEAN ICE Data Management Plan (DMP), and it is based on the Horizon Europe Data Management Plan (DMP) template. OCEAN ICE moves beyond

open access in implementing open science practices while following Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability (FAIR) principles. It applies to research data collected during the project as well as to publications. OCEANICE uses and contributes to international standards, uses open data management software tools (ERDDAP, GeoServer, GeoNetwork, GitHub and Zenodo), and develops innovative open science approaches to data use (Python scripts, colabs, etc.).

Project digital outcomes are made freely available under Creative Commons/Open Data Commons licensing.

12. Updates of the DMP

This DMP will be updated in month 36.

13. References

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Annex 1 – Data inventory

Planned measurements

Tab. 3: Mooring.

Activity	Lead Beneficiary	Due Date (month)	DOI	Data source
M9 Deployment of moorings in South Sandwich Trench	UKRI-BAS	30/04/2023 (6M)	https://zenodo.org/records/10868956	https://github.com/RJArthern/KalmanEnsembling.git
M4 Instrument deployment through Fimbul Ice Shelf borehole	UKRI-BAS	31/12/2023 (14M)	https://zenodo.org/records/10225406	
M2 Deployment of various moored instruments	AWI	31/10/2024 (24M)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14013295	The expected data will be made available through the deliverable D1.6
M10 Recovery of moorings in South Sandwich Trench	UKRI-BAS	30/04/2025 (30M)	https://zenodo.org/records/15190926	The quality-controlled dataset will form deliverable D5.1, Mooring dataset from South Sandwich Trench (31/10/2025)
D1.6 Deployment of bottom pressure recorders	UKRI-BAS	30/09/2025 (36M)		
D5.1 Mooring dataset from South Sandwich Trench	UKRI-BAS	31/10/2025		
D2.4 Observations of the ocean beneath	UKRI-BAS	30/09/2025 (36M)		

Fimbul Ice Shelf				
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Tab. 4: AUV.

Activity	Lead Beneficiary	Due Date (month)	DOI	Data source
M3 Deployment of AUV in the Amundsen Sea	UGOT	31/12/2023 (14M)	https://zenodo.org/records/10246301	
D2.2 AUV observations under the sea-ice around grounded icebergs	UGOT	31/10/2024 (24M)	https://zenodo.org/records/13951229	https://doi.org/10.5878/349w-b176
D2.3 Ship and AUV observations near /within a warm ice-shelf cavity	UGOT	31/10/2024 (24M)		

Tab. 5: Argo.

Activity	Lead Beneficiary	Due Date (month)	DOI	Data source
M1 Deployment of 3 pairs of Argo floats	UKRI-BAS	31/10/2024 (24M)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13785339	https://fleetmonitoring.eu-ro-argo.eu/float/1902687 https://fleetmonitoring.eu-ro-argo.eu/float/5907093 https://fleetmonitoring.eu-ro-argo.eu/float/4903786 https://fleetmonitoring.eu-ro-argo.eu/float/3902582 https://fleetmonitoring.eu-ro-argo.eu/float/6990622 https://fleetmonitoring.eu-ro-argo.eu/float/4903780 https://fleetmonitoring.eu-ro-argo.eu/float/5907087 https://fleetmonitoring.eu-ro-argo.eu/float/6990621
D1.5 Deployment of profiling floats as pairs	UKRI-BAS	31/03/2026 (42M)		

Tab. 6: Drifting buoys.

Activity	Lead Beneficiary	Due Date (month)
Polarstern cruise to East Antarctic, the Amery Ice Shelf, at the end of the year 2023 - floats to be sent along	AWI	31/03/2026 (42M)
Floats on the cruise from Japan with international collaborator Shigeru Aoki (Aoki's project)	UKRI-BAS	31/03/2026 (42M)
Floats in either the Amundsen or the eastern Ross Sea	UKRI-BAS	31/03/2026 (42M)

Data inventory

Tab. 7. Data inventory.

Name	OCEAN ICE ERDDAP link	Link to source	Link to metadata	Link to DOI	Citation
Iceberg grounding enhances the release of freshwater on the Antarctic continental shelf		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15747365	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15747365	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15747365	Olivé Abelló, A., Mathiot, P., Jourdain, N., Kostov, Yavor, Holland, P., Gascoin, S., & Rousset, C. (2025). Olivé Abelló et al., 2025 dataset - Iceberg grounding enhances the release of freshwater on the Antarctic continental shelf [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15747365
		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15528376	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15528376	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15528376	Olivé Abelló, A., Mathiot, P., Jourdain, N., Kostov, Yavor, Holland, P., Gascoin, S., & Rousset, C. (2025). Olivé Abelló et al., 2025 dataset - Iceberg grounding enhances the release of freshwater on the Antarctic continental shelf [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15528376
Contribution of continental-scale ice dynamics processes to freshwater fluxes		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15590997	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15590997	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15590997	Millan, R., Barré, J.-B., & Moncada, F. (2025). Datasets of the deliverable D3.1 - EO: Contribution of continental scale ice dynamics processes to freshwater fluxes [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15590997
Updates to the NEMO iceberg dynamics and grounding (Version 2).		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15484879	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15484879	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15484879	Yavor Kostov. (2025). Kostov et al 2025. Updates to the NEMO iceberg dynamics and grounding (Version 2). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15484879
FESOM 2. Circumpolar Simulation (1991-2020) /TS		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15189061	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15189061	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15189061	van Caspel, M. (2025). FESOM 2. Circumpolar Simulation (1991-2020) /TS [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15189061
FESOM 2. Bellingshausen and Amundsen Seas Experiment (1991-2020) / TS		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15267996	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15267996	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15267996	van Caspel, M. (2025). FESOM 2. Bellingshausen and Amundsen Seas Experiment (1991-2020) / TS [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15267996

FESOM 2. West and Shackleton Ice Shelf Experiment (1991-2020) / TS		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15268272	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15268272	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15268272	van Caspel, M. (2025). FESOM 2. West and Shackleton Ice Shelf Experiment (1991-2020) / TS [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15268272
FESOM 2. Eastern Weddell Sea Experiment (1991-2020) / TS		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15268317	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15268317	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15268317	van Caspel, M. (2025). FESOM 2. Eastern Weddell Sea Experiment (1991-2020) / TS [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15268317
FESOM 2. West and Shackleton Ice Shelf Experiment (1991-2020) / UV		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15299425	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15299425	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15299425	van Caspel, M., Janout, M., & Timmermann, R. (2025). FESOM 2. West and Shackleton Ice Shelf Experiment (1991-2020) / UV [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15299425
FESOM 2. FESOM 2. Bellingshausen and Amundsen Seas Experiment (1991-2020) / UV		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15299650	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15299650	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15299650	van Caspel, M., Janout, M., & Timmermann, R. (2025). FESOM 2. Bellingshausen and Amundsen Seas Experiment (1991-2020) / UV [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15299650
FESOM 2. Eastern Weddell Sea Experiment (1991-2020) / UV		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15299705	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15299705	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15299705	van Caspel, M., Janout, M., & Timmermann, R. (2025). FESOM 2. Eastern Weddell Sea Experiment (1991-2020) / UV [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15299705
FESOM 2. Circumpolar Simulation (1991-2020) /UV		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15280675	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15280675	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15280675	van Caspel, M., Janout, M., & Timmermann, R. (2025). FESOM 2. Circumpolar Simulation (1991-2020) /UV [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15280675
Optimized Physical Tracer (OPT) reconstructions for past global ocean surface temperature, salinity and stable oxygen isotopes. (1.0)		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15181349	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15181349	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15181349	Davila Rodriguez, X., McDonagh, E., Hamilton, B., & Gebbie, G. (2025). Optimized Physical Tracer (OPT) reconstructions for past global ocean surface temperature, salinity and stable oxygen isotopes. (1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15181349
NEMO4.2 eORCA1 configuration files for stable millennial ocean simulations (1.0)		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14041098	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14041098	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14041098	de Lavergne, C., Rathore, S., Madec, G., Sallée, J.-B., Ethé, C., Nasser, A.-A., Millet, B., & Vancoppenolle, M. (2024). NEMO4.2 eORCA1 configuration files for stable millennial ocean simulations (1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14041098
Subglacial fresh-water discharge from the AIS	This work quantifies basal melt rates in	https://github.com/GHilmarG/UaSource	https://zenodo.org/records/14193326	https://zenodo.org/records/14193326	https://zenodo.org/records/14193326

<p>into the Southern Ocean (D3.3)</p>	<p>the Antarctic Ice Sheet caused by ice sliding, using surface velocity data to tightly constrain ice flow and bed stress estimates. Basal water production in fast-flow areas reaches meters per year, far exceeding melt from geothermal heat. A new subglacial water-routing algorithm was also developed, avoiding resolution issues of previous methods.</p>				
<p>Freshwater Sources in the Global Ocean through Salinity-d18O Relationships: A Machine Learning Solution to a Water Mass Problem</p>	<p>This dataset contains point estimates of meteoric water and sea ice meltwater fraction in the ocean polar watermasses, as well as the global stable oxygen isotopic composition (d18O) of meteoric water. These estimates were inferred from co-located d18O, salinity and temperature observations from NASA-GISS (Schmidt et al., 1999) and CISE-LOCEAN (Reverdin et al.,</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/record/16992714</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/16992714</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/16992714</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/16992714</p>

	<p>2022) datasets, as well as individual cruise data available at the British Oceanographic Data Centre (https://www.bodc.ac.uk/), through the Self Organizing Map machine learning approach to identify distinct salinity-d18O relationships in water masses. More information can be found in the associated manuscript Davila et al. (2025).</p>				
<p>Deployment of moorings in South Sandwich Trench (Milestone MS9)</p>	<p>IEnKS algorithm for initialising coupled ice - ocean models</p>	<p>https://github.com/RJArthurn/KalmanEnsembling</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/10868956</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/10868956</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/10868956</p>
<p>AUV observations under the sea-ice around grounded icebergs</p>	<p>High resolution bathymetry data set, obtained with an AUV-mounted multibeam, in an ice-covered region near Bear Ridge in the Amundsen Sea. In total 25 km2 of high resolution (1 m grid size) bathymetry were obtained. This can be compared to the resolution normally obtained from a</p>	<p>https://snd.se/en</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/13951229</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/13951229</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/13951229</p>

	<p>ship-borne multibeam, which is 10-20 m. An initial assessment of the traces seen is also provided.</p>				
<p>Future freshwater fluxes from the Antarctic ice sheet</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/griddap/SSP585_FWF_1990_2300_ZwallyBasins.html https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/griddap/SSP126_FWF_1990_2300_ZwallyBasins.html https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/griddap/SSP585_FWF_1990_2300_OceanSectors.html https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/griddap/SSP126_FWF_1990_2300_OceanSectors.html https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/griddap/SSP585_FWF_1990_2300_AIS.html https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/griddap/SSP126_FWF_1990_2300_AIS.html</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14162776</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14162776</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14162776</p>	<p>Coulon, V., De Rydt, J., Gregov, T., Qin, Q., & Pattyn, F. (2024). Future freshwater fluxes from the Antarctic ice sheet [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14162776</p>
<p>AAD - ASPeCt-Bio: Chlorophyll a in Antarctic sea ice from historical ice core dataset (1983 - 2008)</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/taledap/AAD_ASPeCt-Bio_historical.html</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/taledap/AAD_ASPeCt-Bio_historical.html</p>	<p>https://data.aad.gov.au/metadata/ASPeCt-Bio</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.1029/2012GL053478</p>	<p>M. Meiners, M. Vancoppenolle, S. Thanassekos, G. S. Dieckmann, D. N. Thomas, J.-L. Tison, K. R. Arrigo, D. Garrison, A. McMinn, D. Lannuzel, P. van der Merwe, K. M. Swadling, W. O. Smith Jr., I. Melnikov, B. Raymond (2012) Chlorophyll a in Antarctic sea ice from historical ice core data. GEOPHYSICAL RESEARCH LETTERS, VOL. 39, L21602, doi:10.1029/2012GL053478, 2012.</p>

<p>AADC (2019) Extract of data from the sea ice measurements database - 1985-2007</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/AADC_sea_ice_measurements_database_1985_2007.html</p>	<p>https://data.aad.gov.au/metadata/sea_ice_measurements_database</p>	<p>https://data.aad.gov.au/metadata/sea_ice_measurements_database</p>	<p>http://dx.doi.org/doi:10.26179/5cecce40a20b0</p>	<p>These data were collected and made available by the SO-CHIC project and the programs that contribute to it</p>
<p>AMUNDSEN CRUISES DB</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/AMUNDSEN_CRUISES.html</p>	<p>https://data.arice-h2020.eu/</p>	<p>https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/ba56b242-00de-492c-99ca-2cd1fbdf99bf https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6905b1bf-0562-4d22-8963-9c71f3f9bf21 https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/5ecb7d3b-3802-4def-8e57-0988ea54498d https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/94d17e58-8769-4d07-ad9d-5864b08847c1 https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/4f67a96a-ea9e-4ec1-bb16-157fbf7a59b0 https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/a11eac04-c967-4ea2-8ff3-c40ebc75c66f https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/a9756a0fa-4d04-4cae-8e60-fcb600fe2e6b</p>		

			https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/en/catalog.search#/metadatan/a/b48e7870-278d-43fb-b735-1a589c6e2c3d		
Antarctic Tide Gauge Database	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/ANT_TG_OCEAN_HEIGHT.html	https://www.usap-dc.org/view/dataset/601358	https://www.usap-dc.org/view/dataset/601358	https://doi.org/10.15784/601358	Howard, S. L., King, M., & Padman, L. (2020) "Antarctic Tide Gauge Database, version 1" U.S. Antarctic Program (USAP) Data Center. doi: https://doi.org/10.15784/601358 .
ARCTICNET CRUISES DB	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/ARCTICNET_CRUISES.html	https://data.arice-h2020.eu/	<p>https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/en/catalog.search#/metadatan/ea0dee0a-a9ce-4d38-9f36-f0afc8718142</p> <p>https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/en/catalog.search#/metadatan/8df21a97-b47f-4346-be4e-5051e69af1af</p> <p>https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/en/catalog.search#/metadatan/33585efb-4aea-4dbe-a7e0-5d2335c320e4</p> <p>https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/en/catalog.search#/metadatan/bbd8bbc9-4cbb-4806-a066-b8e5c7c09845</p> <p>https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/en/catalog.search#/metadatan/6c2742ae-b77f-4db1-a69e-7477884e5d4c</p> <p>https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/en/catalog.search#/metadatan/204acfc4-d955-47de-8f07-7cd41dc77151</p> <p>https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/en</p>		

			<p>g/catalog.search#/metadat a/ae859234-c0b4-429a-8a b4-1b9db71393e6 https://metadata.arice-h2 020.eu/geonetwork/srv/en g/catalog.search#/metadat a/f02b5ec8-0155-42f2-a1f 3-969c27130fb3 https://metadata.arice-h2 020.eu/geonetwork/srv/en g/catalog.search#/metadat a/5c6e498d-3f9f-48da-99e b-886cb80752fa https://metadata.arice-h2 020.eu/geonetwork/srv/en g/catalog.search#/metadat a/17069c66-f911-4707-bb 57-b5bcd65e39d6 https://metadata.arice-h2 020.eu/geonetwork/srv/en g/catalog.search#/metadat a/5cd1dcd2-c1db-43da-81 d6-58c9aad17593 https://metadata.arice-h2 020.eu/geonetwork/srv/en g/catalog.search#/metadat a/27d14b71-8804-4e26-97 7b-8546fadbe4f3 https://metadata.arice-h2 020.eu/geonetwork/srv/en g/catalog.search#/metadat a/b87c4cc9-b0cf-4ec4-b0a 0-28669d938e39 https://metadata.arice-h2 020.eu/geonetwork/srv/en g/catalog.search#/metadat a/e4209117-bf63-468a-97 27-91f577ba1359 https://metadata.arice-h2 020.eu/geonetwork/srv/en g/catalog.search#/metadat</p>		
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			<p>a/2c67c7ad-c40e-4b5f-b61d-4d1e845189e7 https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/a/bebc378f-fd8b-459b-a1cc-ad7755ce6fc3 https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/a/6799e8b3-9918-46a1-b5d8-f3114f181096 https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/a/a9562e3b-3051-4117-b232-ef0a33b129c1 https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/a/fb72909c-f133-4782-a500-80fc0a9e87b0 https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/a/8094cee1-9544-43f7-b075-2b8b27baa853 https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/a/89a05741-17d6-4ed6-a42b-99e609433c3e https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/a/d8473bb5-0ca7-4f45-b10b-c6e08d19081d https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/a/f0c9cb05-44e5-47cd-b6</p>		
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			<p>83-5353f6736352 https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/en/catalog.search#/metadata/b541a633-89bb-49f7-86be-67d6b86627a5 https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/en/catalog.search#/metadata/2a5c670f-185a-40ff-a5f7-8f361b50b737 https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/en/catalog.search#/metadata/f1b66fe2-75e0-4ac1-b6ed-29aa2c34e62c https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/en/catalog.search#/metadata/bb51ad74-4af9-44a9-9e8d-27f4b75e36dd https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/en/catalog.search#/metadata/fda3bec4-0b21-4078-b32a-753437ec75e3 https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/en/catalog.search#/metadata/6d3b7732-65d3-4c6b-9e00-6a3c80c342f4 https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/en/catalog.search#/metadata/df64951b-091a-466b-b687-9aab39c6de8f https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/en/catalog.search#/metadata/5d934f9a-f885-4ef4-87d8-a57d85aee393</p>		
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			<p>https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/a5b8e87b-7278-4679-8fe2-1d8f5059c28c</p> <p>https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/a7e4d12bc-1f5f-434b-bc1d-d42f834b0358</p> <p>https://metadata.arice-h2020.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/a/c4466264-9959-4ba4-9f3e-d00ede3bf8b1?tab=search</p>		
Australian Antarctic Program Survey Webcams	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/Australian_Antarctic_Program.html	https://www.antarctica.gov.au/antarctic-operations/webcams/			
British Antarctica Survey Webcams	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/British_Antarctica_Survey_webcams.html	https://www.bas.ac.uk/data/our-data/images/webcams/			
CCHDO Bottle Data	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/CCHDO_Bottle.html	https://data.pmel.noaa.gov/generic/erddap/tabledap/cchdo_bottle.html			
CCHDO CTD Data	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/CCHDO_CTD.html	https://data.pmel.noaa.gov/generic/erddap/tabledap/cchdo_ctd.html	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3247384	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3247384	Henry, T., Robinson, C., Haumann, F.A., Thomas, J., Hutchings, J., Schuback, N., Tsukernik, M. and Leonard, K. (2019) Physical and biogeochemical oceanography from Conductivity, Temperature, Depth (CTD) rosette deployments during the Antarctic Circumnavigation Expedition (ACE). (Version 1.0), [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3247384
CMEMS - CORA: Coriolis Ocean database for ReAnalysis	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/griddap/INSITU_GLO_PHY	https://www.seanoe.org/data/00351/46219/	https://www.seanoe.org/data/00351/46219/	https://doi.org/10.17882/46219	Szekely Tanguy, Gourrion Jerome, Pouliquen Sylvie, Reverdin Gilles (2025). CORA, Coriolis Ocean Dataset for Reanalysis. SEANOE. https://doi.org/10.17882/46219

	TS OA MY 013 05 2.html				
Collection of XBT performed on the high density line IX28 (Dumont d Urville-Hobart) - 1990-2020	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/SURVOSTRAL.html	https://campagnes.flotteoceanographique.fr/series/172/	https://campagnes.flotteoceanographique.fr/series/172/	https://doi.org/10.18142/172	MORROW-GREINER Rosemary (1992) SURVOSTRAL, https://doi.org/10.18142/172
CTD (data from NISKIN Bottles) LB21 ARCTIC Cruise Italian Arctic project CASSANDRA	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/IADC_ctd_cassandra_bottle.html	https://metadata.iadc.cnr.it/geonetwork/srv/api/records/f7474404-3331-43e5-883b-25755e94956d	https://metadata.iadc.cnr.it/geonetwork/srv/api/records/f7474404-3331-43e5-883b-25755e94956d		
CTD (DOWNCAST) LB21 ARCTIC Cruise Italian Arctic project CASSANDRA	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/IADC_ctd_cassandra_downcast.html	https://metadata.iadc.cnr.it/geonetwork/srv/api/records/c082c3ca-40bf-42b1-a61a-7b3697ab2c5a	https://metadata.iadc.cnr.it/geonetwork/srv/api/records/c082c3ca-40bf-42b1-a61a-7b3697ab2c5a		
CTD data set from mooring S1 @ 1000 m	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/info/IADC_s1_ctd/index.html	https://metadata.iadc.cnr.it/geonetwork/srv/api/records/2298c267-0e42-4bb8-8196-d2076fdf6d8e	https://metadata.iadc.cnr.it/geonetwork/srv/api/records/2298c267-0e42-4bb8-8196-d2076fdf6d8e	https://doi.org/10.71761/2298c267-0e42-4bb8-8196-d2076fdf6d8e	
Daily Southern Ocean Sea Level Anomaly And Geostrophic Currents from multimission altimetry, 2013-2019	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/griddap/seanoeslev_anomaly_geostrophic_currents.html	https://www.aviso.altimetry.fr/en/home.html			
ISAR L2 SST product	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/DATA_TRAWLER_SST.html	https://marlin.csiro.au/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/bdf91f86-2968-4711-873e-2761383bb207	https://marlin.csiro.au/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/bdf91f86-2968-4711-873e-2761383bb207		ISAR-5D Procedures Manual at http://www.isar.org.uk/sites/isar/files/documents/Procedures_manual_v1.01.pdf , 18th GHRST Science Team Meeting extended abstract at http://imos.org.au/fileadmin/user_upload/shared/SOOP/SST_2016/Beggs_IMOS_Ship_SST_for_Satellite_SST_Validation_2017_11Jul2017.pdf , Wimmer, W. and I. Robinson, 2016: The ISAR instrument uncertainty model. J. Atmos. Oceanic Technol. at

					https://journals.ametsoc.org/doi/abs/10.1175/JTECH-D-16-0096.1s
MEOP - Animal-borne Profiles	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/MEOP_Animal-borne_profiles.html	https://www.meop.net/database/meop-databases/meop-ctd-database.html	https://www.seanoe.org/data/00343/45461/	https://doi.org/10.17882/45461	Please refer to https://www.meop.net/database/how-to-cite.html on how to cite these data appropriately.
Monthly climatology fields for product GLOBAL_REANALYSIS_PHY_001_030	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/griddap/GLORYS12V1_sea_floor_potential_temp.html		http://marine.copernicus.eu/documents/PUM/CME-MS-GLO-PUM-001-030.pdf http://marine.copernicus.eu/documents/QUID/CME-MS-GLO-QUID-001-030.pdf	https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00021	
Network for the Collection of Knowledge on melt of Antarctic ice shelves (NECKLACE)	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/NECKLACE.html		https://necklaceproject.com/		Network for the Collection of Knowledge on melt of Antarctic ice shelves (NECKLACE). [YEAR]. Available at https://necklaceproject.com/ . Accessed via soosmap.aq on [YYYY-MM-DD].
NOAA - Optimum Interpolation (OI) Sea Surface Temperature (SST) V2 High Resolution Dataset	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/griddap/NOAA_OISST_v2.html	https://psl.noaa.gov/data/gridded/data.noaa.oisst.v2.highres.html	https://psl.noaa.gov/data/gridded/data.noaa.oisst.v2.highres.html		Huang, B., C. Liu, V. Banzon, E. Freeman, G. Graham, B. Hankins, T. Smith, and H.-M. Zhang, 2021: Improvements of the Daily Optimum Interpolation Sea Surface Temperature (DOISST) Version 2.1, Journal of Climate, 34, 2923-2939. doi: 10.1175/JCLI-D-20-0166.1
NOAA - Surface Ocean CO2 Atlas Database Version 2024 (SOCAT v2024)	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/griddap/SOCATv2024_tracks_gridded_monthly.html	https://socat.info/index.php/data-access/	https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/access/metadata/landing-page/bin/iso?id=gov.noaa.nodc:0293257	https://doi.org/10.25921/9wpm-th28	Bakker et al. (2016) & Sabine et al. (2013)
Float deployment and data delivery to the community via ARGO servers (Milestone MS29)	Within the OCEAN ICE project, the deployment of six profiling floats, Argo ARVOR, perpendicularly to the Bransfield front area at the Strait has been implemented in March 2025. The floats dataset are quality-controlled	https://fleetmonitoring.eu-ro-argo.eu/float/7902290 https://fleetmonitoring.eu-ro-argo.eu/float/2903996 https://fleetmonitoring.eu-ro-argo.eu/float/5907175 https://fleetmonitoring.eu-ro-argo.eu/float/3902667 https://fleetmonitoring.eu-ro-argo.eu/float/4903872	https://zenodo.org/records/16628744	https://zenodo.org/records/16628744	Shapel, N. (2025). Float deployment and data delivery to the community via ARGO servers (Milestone MS29). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16628744

	and uploaded regularly with the help of Coriolis and Euro-Argo to the https://dataselection.euro-argo.eu/ and https://www.oceanops.org/board				
OCEAN ICE - Argo DE - Deployment of 4 Argo float profilers	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/ARGO_FLOATS_OCEANICE_DE.html	https://www.seanoe.org/data/00311/42182/	https://www.seanoe.org/data/00311/42182/	https://zenodo.org/records/13785339	Argo (2025). Argo float data and metadata from Global Data Assembly Centre (Argo GDAC). SEANOE. https://doi.org/10.17882/42182
OCEAN ICE - Argo UK - Deployment of 4 Argo float profilers	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/ARGO_FLOATS_OCEANICE_UK.html	https://www.seanoe.org/data/00311/42182/	https://www.seanoe.org/data/00311/42182/	https://zenodo.org/records/13785339	Argo (2025). Argo float data and metadata from Global Data Assembly Centre (Argo GDAC). SEANOE. https://doi.org/10.17882/42182
OCEAN ICE - European circumpolar sea ice production fluxes	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/griddap/EU_circumpolar_seaice_prod_fluxes_1992_2023.html	https://gitlab.awi.de/ocean-ice/deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/11652686	https://zenodo.org/records/11652686	Kaleschke, L. (2024). EU project OCEAN:ICE Deliverable: D1.4 Gridded European circumpolar sea ice production fluxes [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11652686
OCEAN ICE - Pan-Antarctic (90S-45S) temperature and salinity profiles compilation	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/seanoe_ctemp_a_sal_profile_90S45S.html	https://www.seanoe.org/data/00886/99787/	https://www.seanoe.org/data/00886/99787/	https://zenodo.org/records/11096059	Zhou Shenjie, Dutrieux Pierre, Giulivi Claudia, Lee Won Sang, Kim Tae-Wan, Hattermann Tore, Janout Markus (2024). Southern Ocean (90°S-45°S) conservative temperature and absolute salinity profiles compilation (OCEAN ICE D1.1). SEANOE. https://doi.org/10.17882/99787
OCEAN ICE - Pan-Antarctic (90°S-60°S) moored time series compilation	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/seanoe_moored_time_series_south60S.html	https://www.seanoe.org/data/00887/99922/	https://www.seanoe.org/data/00887/99922/	https://zenodo.org/records/11096059	Zhou Shenjie, Dutrieux Pierre, Giulivi Claudia, Silvano Alessandro, Auckland Christopher, Abrahamsen Povl, Meredith Michael, Vaňková Irena, Nicholls Keith, Davis Peter, Østerhus Svein, Gordon Arnold, Zappa Christopher, Sebaginazzi Dotto Tiago, Scambos Ted, Gunn Kathryn, Rintoul Steve, Aoki Shigeru, Stevens Craig, Liu Chengyan, Kim Tae-Wan, Lee Won San, Janout Markus, Hattermann Tore, Lauber Julius, Darelus Elin, Wåhlin Anna, Middleton Leo, Castagno Pasquale, Budillon Giorgio, Heywood Karen, Graham Jennifer, Dye Stephen, Hirano Daisuke, Miller Una Kim (2025). Southern Ocean moored time series (south of 60°S) (OCEAN ICE D1.1). SEANOE.

					<p>https://doi.org/10.17882/99922</p> <p>Zhou Shenjie, Dutrieux Pierre, Giulivi Claudia F., Jenkins Adrian, Silvano Alessandro, Auckland Christopher, Abrahamsen E. Povl, Meredith Michael P., Vaňková Irena, Nicholls Keith W., Davis Peter E. D., Østerhus Svein, Gordon Arnold L., Zappa Christopher J., Dotto Tiago S., Scambos Theodore A., Gunn Kathryn L., Rintoul Stephen R., Aoki Shigeru, Stevens Craig, Liu Chengyan, Yun Sukyoung, Kim Tae-Wan, Lee Won Sang, Janout Markus, Hattermann Tore, Lauber Julius, Darelus Elin, Wåhlin Anna, Middleton Leo, Castagno Pasquale, Budillon Giorgio, Heywood Karen J., Graham Jennifer, Dye Stephen, Hirano Daisuke, Miller Una Kim (2025). The OCEAN ICE mooring compilation: a standardised, pan-Antarctic database of ocean hydrography and current time series. https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-2025-54</p>
<p>OCEAN ICE - Trace gas measurements, basal glacial meltwater fractions, and water ages during RV POLARSTERN cruise PS124, Southern Weddell Sea</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/Weddell_Sea_water_mass_age_melt_water_fractions.html</p>	<p>https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.971321</p>	<p>https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.971321</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/12581210</p>	<p>Huhn, Oliver; Janout, Markus A; Sültenfuß, Jürgen; Bulsiewicz, Klaus; Hinse, Yannik (2024): Trace gas measurements, basal glacial meltwater fractions, and water ages during RV POLARSTERN cruise PS124, Southern Weddell Sea, 2021 [dataset]. PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.971321</p>
<p>Physical and biogeochemical oceanography data from Conductivity, Temperature, Depth (Bottle) rosette deployments during the Antarctic Circumnavigation Expedition (ACE)</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/ACE_bottle_CTD_20200406CURRSGC_MR.html</p>	<p>https://swisspolar.ch/expeditions/ace/ace-data/</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/3813646</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/3813646</p>	<p>Henry, T., Robinson, C., Haumann, F. A., Thomas, J., Hutchings, J., Schuback, N., Tsukernik, M., & Leonard, K. (2020). Physical and biogeochemical oceanography data from Conductivity, Temperature, Depth (CTD) rosette deployments during the Antarctic Circumnavigation Expedition (ACE). (1.1). Zenodo</p>
<p>Physical and biogeochemical oceanography data from Conductivity,</p>	<p>https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/ACE_ctd_CTD202</p>	<p>https://swisspolar.ch/expeditions/ace/ace-data/</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/3813646</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/3813646</p>	<p>Henry, T., Robinson, C., Haumann, F. A., Thomas, J., Hutchings, J., Schuback, N., Tsukernik, M., & Leonard, K. (2020). Physical and biogeochemical oceanography data from Conductivity, Temperature, Depth (CTD) rosette</p>

Temperature, Depth (CTD) rosette deployments during the Antarctic Circumnavigation Expedition (ACE)	00406CURRSGCMR.html				deployments during the Antarctic Circumnavigation Expedition (ACE). (1.1). Zenodo
POLARSTERN CRUISES DB	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/POLARSTERN_CRUISES.html	https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.860066	https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.860066	https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.860066	Rohardt, Gerd; Fahrbach, Eberhard; Beszczynska-Möller, Agnieszka; Boetius, Antje; Brunßen, Jutta; Budéus, Gereon; Cisewski, Boris; Engbrodt, Ralph; Gauger, Steffen; Geibert, Walter; Geprägs, Patrizia; Gerdes, Dieter; Gersonde, Rainer; Gordon, Arnold L; Hellmer, Hartmut H; Isla, Enrique; Jacobs, Stanley S; Janout, Markus A; Jokat, Wilfried; Klages, Michael; Kuhn, Gerhard; Meincke, Jens; Ober, Sven; Østerhus, Svein; Peterson, Ray G; Rabe, Benjamin; Rudels, Bert; Schauer, Ursula; Schröder, Michael; Sildam, Jüri; Soltwedel, Thomas; Stangeew, Elena; Stein, Manfred; Strass, Volker H; Thiede, Jörn; Tippenhauer, Sandra; Veth, Cornelis; von Appen, Wilken-Jon; Weirig, Marie-France; Wisotzki, Andreas; Wolf-Gladrow, Dieter A; Kanzow, Torsten (2016): Physical oceanography on board of POLARSTERN (1983-11-22 to 2016-02-14) [dataset]. Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research, Bremerhaven, PANGAEA, https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.860066 ,
PSMSL - Absolute Sea Level Trend	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/griddap/PSMSL_Absolute_sea_level_trend.html	https://erddap.sochic-h2020.eu/erddap/files/EP_ERD_SOO_BIOA_NN_NN_118/	https://psmsl.org/data/obtainning/complete.php	https://doi.org/10.2112/JCOASTRES-D-12-00175.1	Simon J. Holgate, Andrew Matthews, Philip L. Woodworth, Lesley J. Rickards, Mark E. Tamisiea, Elizabeth Bradshaw, Peter R. Foden, Kathleen M. Gordon, Svetlana Jevrejeva, and Jeff Pugh "New Data Systems and Products at the Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level," Journal of Coastal Research 29(3), 493-504, (1 May 2013). https://doi.org/10.2112/JCOASTRES-D-12-00175.1
SCAR - International Iceberg Database	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/NPI_Iceberg_database.html	https://data.npolar.no/dataset/e4b9a604-1b64-4890-9f21-56b5589807c4	https://data.npolar.no/dataset/e4b9a604-1b64-4890-9f21-56b5589807c4	https://doi.org/10.21334/NPOLAR.2021.E4B9A604	Orheim, O., Giles, B., Moholdt, G., Jacka, J., Bjørndal, A. (2021). The SCAR International Iceberg Database [Data set]. Norwegian Polar Institute. https://doi.org/10.21334/npolar.2021.e4b9a604
SO-CHIC - Continuous meteorological surface measurement conducted during	https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/SOCHIC_Cruise_2022_Agulhas_II_met.html	https://zenodo.org/records/6948850	https://zenodo.org/records/6948850	https://zenodo.org/records/6948850	Ward, Brian, Azevedo, Alexandra, Binase, Zanele, ten Doeschate, Anneke, Els, Heino, Hamnca, Siyabulela, Jacobs, Leon, Katsoulis, Michael, Lavanchy, Sebastian, Lavis, Craig, Lourenco, Antonio, du Plessis, Marcel, Rosenthal, Hanna,

Cruise 2022 - AgulhasII					Sallee, Jean-Baptiste, Soares, Bianca, Spira, Theo, & Steiger, Nadine. (2022). SOCHIC cruise report (Version v1).
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Appendix

Tab. 8: OCEAN ICE partners' EDMO code.

Participant organisation	EDMO code	EDMO link
United Kingdom Research and Innovation	4946	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/4946
NORCE Norwegian Research Centre	5153	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/5153
Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut	469	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/469
Alfred-Wegener-Institut Helmholtz-Zentrum Fur Polar-Und Meeresforschung	1368	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/1368
Centre National De La Recherche Scientifique	552	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/552
University of Northumbria at Newcastle	5400	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/5400
University of Southampton	1801	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/1801
Universiteit Utrecht	1627	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/1627
ETT SPA	2764	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/2764
Université Libre de Bruxelles	717	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/717
Ecole Normale Supérieure	4763	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/4763
Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research	3445	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/3445
University of Bristol	1475	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/1475
University of Gothenburg	3984	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/3984
University of Reading	2080	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/2080
Norwegian Polar Institute	1349	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/1349
European Polar Board	5859	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/5859

Tab. 9. Metadata Vocabularies.

Metadata field	Vocabulary exists	Link to vocabulary	Vocabulary governance	Mandatory/ Suggested
Platform id		https://www.ocean-ops.org/	OCEANOPS – WMO	M
Platform type	Yes	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/	BODC	M
sensor_model	Yes	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L22/current/ Sensor URL	BODC -NVS	S
contributors_role				
naming_authority	Yes	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/	SeaDataNet	M
Institution	Yes	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/	SeaDataNet	M
qc_method	*	doi		M
Group parameters	yes	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P02/current/ http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P33/current/	BODC – EMODnet Physics	M
variable names	Yes	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/current/ http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P07/current/ http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/	BODC – NVS	S S M
unit	Yes	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/	SeaDataNet	M
Quality Flag Scheme	Yes	https://vocab.seadatanet.org/v_bodc_vocab_v2/search.asp?lib=L20	SeaDataNet	M
Time	Yes	ISO8601	ISO	M
Datum	Yes	WGS84	ISO	M
Country	Yes	ISO3166	ISO	M
Licence	Yes	https://creativecommons.org/	CC	M
INSPIRE	Yes	ISO 19115	ISO/INSPIRE	M
PI	Yes	https://orcid.org/	ORCID	S

data_doi				S
Project_ID funding_ID	Yes	https://edmerp.seadatanet.org/ https://cordis.europa.eu/	SeaDataNet CORDIS	M
funding_statement				S